

People's Democratic Republic of Algeria
Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research
University of Mustapha Stambouli – Mascara
Faculty of Letters and Languages
Department of English Language and Literature

**Teacher's Attitudes Towards Teacher Collaboration: The Case of the
Department of English at Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara.**

**A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
Master in Didactics of Foreign Languages.**

Submitted by:

Mr. Mohamed El Amine HAMZI

Ms. Habiba BELMOKHTAR

Supervised by:

Prof. Habib YAHIAOUI

Board of Examiners:

President: Dr. Hadjer Belghoul University of Mascara

Supervisor: Prof. Habib Yahiaoui University of Mascara

Examiner: Dr. Miloud Bekkar University of Mascara

Academic Year: 2024/2025

Dedication I

I dedicate this work to my parents, who encouraged me along the journey, who have raised me to be the person I am today.

To my dearest brother and sisters, Abdelkarim, Khadidja, and Hanane, and my nephew, Rafik Iyad.

To my former inspector and great mentor, Mr. Cheref, who stood by my side, and without whom I wouldn't be writing these words.

To my colleagues and friends: Mr. Messeguem, Mr. Mekkaoui, and Mrs. Hezil, who provided me with support and help.

To all my university teachers and classmates.

To my thesis partner Ms. Habiba, whose patience never wavered.

To all those who were there for me.

Dedication II

I dedicate this graduation to the soul of my beloved father whom I never met, yet whose memory lives on in my heart, to the one who departed in body but remains in lasting impact.

To my second Dad Kadi Habib who stepped in when life took my first. Thank you for being my light and strength.

To my dear Mom Najat, who gave up so much so I could go further your love and support have been my source of strength.

To my dear grandparents may God prolong their lives and to my uncles, for their generous support.

To my thesis partner, Amine whose positive influence and valuable support inspired my perseverance.

To all the esteemed teachers throughout my academic journey.

Acknowledgments

In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful. Peace and blessings be upon our Master and beloved Prophet Muhammad.

First and foremost, we would like to express our heartfelt gratitude to our supervisor, **Prof. Habib Yahiaoui**. His invaluable academic guidance, generous time, and constant encouragement have been a guiding light for this work. His patience, insight, and thoughtful advice not only shaped the direction of our research but also inspired us to persist and grow as researchers. We are deeply honoured and grateful to have worked under his supervision.

We also wish to extend our sincere appreciation to the distinguished jury members, **Dr. Bekkar** and **Dr. Belghoul**, for their time, willingness to evaluate this dissertation, and enrich it with their constructive feedback and corrections. Their engagement is deeply appreciated.

This research would not have been possible without the kind participation of the English Department teachers who contributed to the study. We are truly thankful for their openness and willingness to support our work.

A special mention goes to **Dr. Belabbes** and **Dr. Safir**, whose constant support and words of encouragement meant a great deal to us during this academic journey. We also owe sincere thanks to **Dr. Hezil**, **Dr. Sili** and **Dr. Aberrahmane** for their kind assistance, thoughtful contributions, and readiness to help whenever needed.

Finally, we extend our deepest thanks to all those who supported and accompanied us throughout this research process. Your belief in us has been a source of strength and motivation, and for that, we are profoundly grateful.

Abstract

It is indisputable that teaching is a demanding practice that requires time, effort and patience. Having a colleague or a team to share the load and offer support should be regarded as a valuable asset, not a burden, unlike some teachers may believe. This work aims to explore the frequency of teacher collaboration in the Department of English at the University of Mascara. In addition, it attempts to identify the factors that may discourage or obstruct EFL teachers in the department from practising collaboration, which is considered as a variable in improving teachers' instruction, fostering a strong educational environment and leading to better students' outcomes. To address this issue, the researchers adopted a mixed-methods approach to gather valid and objective data, which involved two research tools: the questionnaire and the interview with a sample of 07 EFL teachers in the English Department at the University of Mascara. The findings revealed a limited extent of collaboration among EFL teachers due to a combination of structural, interpersonal and cultural barriers. Thereby, the study successfully achieves its objective. In response to the findings, this study suggests several actionable recommendations for teachers, along with policymakers, to promote teacher collaboration in the department and overcome the identified obstacles, in addition to specific pedagogical suggestions aimed at promoting collaboration at the level of the English Department.

Keywords: Teacher Collaboration, EFL teachers, structural barriers, interpersonal barriers, cultural barriers, pedagogical suggestions.

List of Acronyms

EFL: English as a Foreign Language

SPED: Special Education

PLC: Professional Learning Community

NETs: Native English Teachers

NNETs: Non-Native English Teachers

ESP: English for Specific Purposes

CoP: Communities of Practice

ICT: Information and Communication Technology

PhD: Doctor of Philosophy

L: Licence (L1 refers to 1st year Licence)

M: Master (M1 refers to 1st year Master)

TTU: Teaching Techniques for University (refers to a university module)

MCQ: Multiple Choice Question

AI: Artificial Intelligence

TPs: Tutorial Sessions or (Practical Sessions)

List of Tables

Table 2.1: Levels, Specialisations and Grades in The Department of English at Mustapha Stambouli University.	35
Table 3.1: Participants' Distribution According to the Level and Grades They Teach.	48
Table 3.2: Participants' Distribution According to the Specialisations They Teach.	48
Table 3.3: Participants' Distribution According to the Modules They Teach.	49
Table 3.4: Teacher Collaboration Frequency in the Department.....	50

List of Figures

Figure 1.1: Approaches of Co-teaching.	12
Figure 1.2: Horizontal <i>Algebra 1 Achievement Team</i>	21
Figure 1.3: Vertical <i>ELA Achievement Team</i>	22
Figure 2.1: Faculties of Mustapha Stambouli University	34
Figure 3.1: Participants' Distribution According to their Gender.	47
Figure 3.2: Participants' Distribution According to their Years of Experience.	47
Figure 3.3: Obstacles and Challenges to Teacher Collaboration.	51
Figure 3.4: Teachers' Beliefs on Teacher Collaboration and Professional Development.	53
Figure 3.5: Teachers' Beliefs on Teacher Collaboration and Students' Outcomes.	54
Figure 3.6: Teachers' Beliefs on Teacher Collaboration and University Effectiveness.	55
Figure 3.7: Teachers' Beliefs on Teacher Collaboration and Work Environment.	55
Figure 3.8: Teachers' Readiness and Willingness to Collaborate.	56

Table of Content

Dedication I.....	I
Dedication II.....	II
Acknowledgments.....	III
Abstract.....	IV
List of Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	V
List of Tables.....	VI
List of Figures.....	VII
Table of Content.....	VIII
General Introduction.....	1

Chapter One: Literature Review

Introduction.....	7
Key Concepts.....	7
Definition of Key Concepts.....	8
Teacher Collaboration.....	8
Mentoring.....	8
Co-teaching.....	9
Professional Learning Community (PLC).....	9
The History of Collaboration.....	10
Collaboration in the Algerian Context.....	13

Theoretical Framework of Teacher Collaboration	14
Social Constructivism	14
Communities of Practice (CoP)	15
Benefits of Teacher Collaboration.....	16
Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the Teacher Level	16
Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the School Level	18
Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the Student Level	19
Achievement Teams as a Collaborative Practice.....	20
Horizontal Teams.....	20
Vertical Teams	21
Specialist and Elective Teams.....	22
Barriers Restricting Teacher Collaboration	22
Structural Barriers	23
Interpersonal Barriers.....	23
Cultural Barriers.....	24
Conclusion	25

Chapter Two: Research Methodology

Introduction	29
Objective of The Study.....	30
Research Questions.....	30
Hypotheses.....	30

Research design	31
Research Methodology	32
Case Study	32
Description of Setting	33
Sampling	35
Population of the study	36
Piloting.....	36
Research Tools	37
Questionnaire	37
Interview	40
Data Analysis Methods.....	41
Quantitative Data Analysis	42
Qualitative Data Analysis	42
Conclusion	43

Chapter Three: Data Analysis

Introduction	46
Data Analysis Tools.....	46
Questionnaire Analysis and Interpretations	46
Interview Analysis and Interpretations	56
Discussion.....	64
Limitations.....	70

Recommendations	71
Conclusion	74
General Conclusion	77
References	80
Appendices	85
Appendix A.....	86
Appendix B.....	89
الملخص	91
Résumé	92

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

General Introduction

Teaching is an extremely demanding profession that requires patience and time to achieve perfection. In fact, with time, teachers gain experience and keep adjusting themselves to the continuous demands of the aforementioned profession. The issue linked to teaching is that policymakers frequently run out of time, so they recruit teachers and put them in the crucible with no training whatsoever. Felder and Brent (2016) raised this issue and made the analogy of teaching as being handed the keys of a car without being taught how to drive. The result is that even professors with a certain degree of experience can wind up driving with the pedagogical brakes on. This type of driving often results in significant harm to innocent learners who are eager to acquire knowledge.

How do novice teachers cope with situations? Most have only one model: the way they were taught, lectured, and assessed. One thing is for sure: there are better alternatives that novice teachers often overlook. By collaborating, we can share and transmit these alternatives from generation to generation.

Individuals cannot live in isolation because human nature is inherently social. Collaboration among teachers is also a sensitive and vital part of teaching. Schmoker (1996) describes that “collaboration allows teachers to benefit from each other’s social intelligence”; that is to say, working together is an effective means that facilitates the process of communication and the exchange of competencies and experiences in a way that serves the educational institution. It also strengthens relationships and contributes to creating an atmosphere of complete trust. For this reason, the issue addressed in this research remains complex and has not been implemented effectively, which negatively affects the performance of the teachers and the educational outcomes of the learners.

General Introduction

The research examines the extent to which teacher collaboration is practised among English as a foreign language university teachers and how this, in turn, impacts overall educational effectiveness. It further sheds light on the underlying reasons and barriers that hinder collaboration among teachers, aiming to achieve a higher scientific standard that positively influences teachers' performance and professional growth and students' academic outcomes.

In the current research, the researchers endeavour to examine the extent of teacher collaboration among EFL University teachers in the Department of English at the University of Mascara and investigate the hindrances and obstacles that may negatively influence their collaborative practices. In light of the above, the study seeks to address the following key questions:

1. To what extent do teachers in the English Department at Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara engage in collaborative practices?
2. What are the main barriers that hinder collaboration among teachers in the English Department?

The research questions lead to the development of the following hypotheses:

1. EFL university teachers collaborate to a limited extent.
2. EFL university teachers' ability to collaborate is negatively influenced by structural barriers, cultural barriers, and interpersonal barriers.

In order to identify teachers' attitudes towards Teacher Collaboration and its role in improving their instruction, widening their knowledge and helping them in achieving their main objective, which is enhancing their learners' outcomes, the researchers have carried out a case study with a sample of 60 EFL University teachers in the Department of English at the

General Introduction

University of Mascara to find out answers to the research questions and confirm or disconfirm the raised hypotheses, aiming to collect reliable and valid data researchers used a mixed-methods approach which involved two different research tool, a questionnaire for a quantitative data which is related to the frequency of Teacher collaboration and an interview for qualitative data which sought to explore the different barriers as a primary objective in addition to the measure of teacher collaboration frequency and its forms as a support to the collected data from the questionnaire.

The Significance of the Study

The current study offers a novel perspective about providing an important opportunity to enhance collaboration among university teachers, including developing teamwork methods and strategies, building close, mutually respectful relationships, and supporting different opinions and viewpoints among them. All of this contributes to creating a comfortable teaching environment for teachers along with a supportive learning environment for students under the slogan “Towards a Purposeful Educational Level to Achieve a Better Level”.

The Structure of the Dissertation

The dissertation breaks down into three distinct chapters. The first chapter, which is the theoretical section, is a *review of* literature. It addresses the main concepts related to the framework of collaboration, as well as explaining the most important stages of the evolutionary process of collaboration. Moreover, it discusses the benefits of teacher collaboration at the level of the teacher, school, and student. In addition, this section reviewed an in-depth analysis of the structure and forms of collaboration, concluding with the most prominent challenges that hindered the progress of effective collaboration, classified into structural, interpersonal and cultural barriers.

General Introduction

The second chapter, titled *Research Methodology*, also known as the practical part, highlights the methods of collecting quantitative and qualitative data on the extent of teachers' collaborative practices in teaching in the English Department. In addition, it provides a comprehensive description of how to design the research and study a case, the sample, and the setting. Moreover, it shows the way in which the collected data was analysed and the methods used to do it.

As for the third chapter, *Data Analysis* is the crux of this research, as it deals with the analyses of the collected data and interprets the most important results revealed after analysing the collected data from the questionnaire and the interviews as research tools with EFL university teachers, concluding with the presentation of some main points and recommendations aimed at exploring future horizons for the benefit of the teacher and the educational system as a whole and suggestions related to future research on the topic.

CHAPTER ONE:
LITERATURE REVIEW

Chapter One: Literature Review

Introduction	7
Key Concepts.....	7
Definition of Key Concepts	8
Teacher Collaboration.....	8
Mentoring.....	8
Co-teaching	9
Professional Learning Community (PLC)	9
The History of Collaboration.....	10
Collaboration in the Algerian Context.....	13
Theoretical Framework of Teacher Collaboration	14
Social Constructivism	14
Communities of Practice (CoP)	15
Benefits of Teacher Collaboration.....	16
Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the Teacher Level	16
Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the School Level	18
Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the Student Level.....	19
Achievement Teams as a Collaborative Practice	20
Horizontal Teams.....	20
Vertical Teams	21
Specialist and Elective Teams	22
Barriers Restricting Teacher Collaboration.....	22
Structural Barriers.....	23
Interpersonal Barriers.....	23
Cultural Barriers.....	24
Conclusion.....	25

Literature Review

Introduction

In the field of education, collaboration among teachers takes various forms, making it a vital subject with strategic dimensions related to the future of Algerian schools and Algerian learners. It is one of the effective factors that contribute to create dynamism and movement within educational units at various educational levels which will: improve the educational performance of the teacher and the educational outcomes of the learner, it will also enable the Algerian school to develop competencies capable of bearing the responsibility of managing the Algerian state in the medium and long term. In this context, this introductory chapter highlights through a review of the literature, the importance of collaboration among teachers.

Key Concepts

This chapter addresses the basic concepts related to collaboration, such as “mentoring, co-teaching, Professional Learning Communities”, and also explains the history of collaboration, including the stages it has gone through, starting from isolation to what it is today in terms of integrated teamwork. It also explores the most important theoretical foundations in the teaching process, including the social structure. It also explores the benefits of collaborative teaching and its role in teachers’ professional development, enhancing students’ outcomes and promoting schools’ performance, in addition to models of collaborative teams among teachers in the form of educational cells that coordinate their work between the elements of a single cell and between the cells of learning materials in the various educational stages. At the same time, this chapter discusses and analyses the most important barriers and challenges that hinder collaboration in the teaching process, which have been classified as structural, interpersonal and cultural barriers.

Definition of Key Concepts

Understanding key concepts is essential in any research study, as it provides clarity and a strong theoretical foundation. In the context of collaboration, defining fundamental terms helps establish a common understanding among educators and researchers. This section explores these concepts by examining different scholarly definitions and perspectives.

Teacher Collaboration

Defining the word “collaboration” is crucial in the field of education. Numerous educational scholars have defined collaboration in many different ways. According to Merriam-Webster’s Collegiate Dictionary (as cited in Honigsfeld & Dove, 2010, p. 5), to collaborate means to work jointly with others or together, especially in an intellectual endeavour. Therefore, the common objective of collaboration is to achieve teaming up especially in activities that include mental effort.

Teacher collaboration is one of the essential elements of education for learners when practitioners work cooperatively, sharing their different ideas and experiences with each other. According to Johnstone and Tsai’s definition (2018), teacher collaboration is “professional interaction with colleagues that focuses on refining and improving classroom instruction, curriculum, and supports for students.” (as cited in Montgomery & Arkiston, 2019, p. 7). This means collaboration supports and promotes student level in the classroom.

Mentoring

In the educational field, mentoring refers to the process of guiding and training early career teachers by experienced and mature teachers through sharing views, competencies, and knowledge they have gained over time. Simply, mentoring can be defined as “sharing

knowledge, skills and experience in order to encourage and empower another person” (Smith, 2020, p. 14). The role of mentoring lies in developing the performance of practitioners and enhancing their skills, all of which can reflect positively and successfully on student learning and achievement in the long run.

Co-teaching

In the educational setting, co-teaching can be defined as an instructional method that brings two or more practitioners in order to provide a distinctive form of education for the learners through their proficiency in a cooperative manner. In the view of (Gately & Gately,2001), co-teaching is “the collaboration between general and special education (SPED) teachers on all of the teaching responsibilities for all of the students assigned to a classroom” (as cited in Honigsfeld & Dove, 2010, p. 6). This concept emphasises the supportiveness and effective mutual collaboration between specialist and general education professionals, all of this contributing to the enhancement and addressing the students' needs.

Professional Learning Community (PLC)

Tutoring is not a simple path, and professional learning communities are generally seen as a beneficial approach for improving educational methods and learner achievement. Professional Learning Communities create an effective environment among practitioners to work together. This priority on collaborative teaching has a vital contribution in fostering better teaching practices and advancing the standards of students' performance (Khasawnah et al., 2023).

Professional Learning community is considered a group of cohesive practitioners coming together to learn, share data gathering and analysis, and discover weaknesses with each other to amplify student outcomes. Newmann (1996) gives his conception of a Professional Learning Community (PLC) which includes five main elements. The professional learning

community is a team in which “teachers have universal views on collaborating, sharing, reflecting, and the needs of their teaching and learning practice”. (Hord, Roussin, & Sommers, 2009, as cited in Xiao Sai & Siraj, 2015, p. 65). That is to say, a professional learning community is a strategy used to enhance relationships between team members and support educators in discussing and evaluating their ideas.

To sum up, Mentoring, co-teaching and PLC are methods focused on collaboration, and shared duties which improve instructional approaches and also create collaborative educational environment among practitioners and learners.

The History of Collaboration

Formerly, teaching was practised in isolation, while the environment in which the teacher worked was very limited in terms of integration and communication with the professional community. In this regard, Flinder (1988, p.19) claims isolation as “a condition under which teachers work”. This perspective sheds light on the surroundings of practitioners, like the deficiency of opportunities in how to communicate and interact with their partners. Previously and on a global level, isolation was a major obstacle in the teaching process, as each teacher practised his profession in a traditional and independent manner, in his own way within his classroom.

According to Lortie (1975, as cited in Schleifer et al., 2017, p. 5), the “Egg-crate” model of school, this concept underlines the individualistic attribute that distinguishes the instructional career, as well as about the little and limited interaction between colleagues and especially how every practitioner works in his specific section separately from each other." This research addressed how practitioners isolated themselves behind their classroom confines, especially the difficulties they face alone and the obstacles related to assessment and instruction they face. For instance, as the guide clarifies (p. 8), Globally and specifically the educational system in

American schools was following the “Egg-crate” model, which greatly affected the lack of systems and structures to improve the performance and encourage collaboration resulting from the isolation of teachers. In the words of Vangriken et al. (2015), “It is more difficult to change the whole school culture and structure than it is to create interventions for teachers and groups of teachers” (p. 36). This exemplifies the idea that changing school culture is a nuanced and demanding process and requires a lot of effort compared to targeted intervention by teachers. Thus, Autonomy was deeper and impactful in tutoring; it was an obstacle in the school system instead of creating programs and workshops that aim to integrate and enhance the confidence among practitioners, it produces a struggle in making collaboration integral.

On the other hand, it is important to ask how collaborative teaching has become nowadays through the use of different methods like PLC, co-teaching etc. In this regard, and in the realm of education there are five approaches of co-teaching clarified by Friend, Reising and Cook (1993, as cited in Aliakbari and Mansouri Nejad 2013, p. 10) the first approach is: “One teaches, one observes” based on two teachers one of them lead the classroom, and the other teacher supporting and observes the learner. The second approach, “parallel teaching” means teachers work with their students by dividing them into workshops, each educator has lesson ownership with their special group. “Station teaching” is the approach in which each teacher should be in charge of the instructional content by breaking the class into small stations and working with them. “Alternative teaching” emphasises the need for special attention and targeted instruction only for teachers who work with a small group of students, whilst the larger group of learners are instructed by another teacher. The last model “team teaching” focuses on when the two teachers work as a “team”. They share roles in teaching students at the same time such as one of them explaining the lesson while the other simplifies ideas. Teachers in this model are a bit like co-presenters at a conference, both teachers do not necessarily plan who takes which part of the lesson, and when one of them makes a point, the other teacher can jump

in and elaborate if needed, yet it is a very difficult approach as it requires extensive planning and it depends on the teacher's methods, thereby it becomes difficult to eliminate diversification in their views.

Figure 1.1: Approaches of Co-teaching.

Source: Adapted from Friend, M., & Bursuck, W. D. (2012). Including students with special needs: A practical guide for classroom teachers (6th ed., p. 77). Merrill.

Among the five co-teaching models clarified previously by Friend, Reising and Cook (1993), four of them were implemented in a Chinese study conducted by Liu (2008, pp. 106-107) about the co-teaching among native English teachers (NETs) and non-native English teachers (NNETs) in a classroom, the study shows that (NETs) should collaborate with (NNETs) especially for Chinese primary school students to address the difficulties they face inside the

classroom due to their lack of understanding of the English language because primary school students are in dire of attention and encouragement than older learner's.

The study by Liu (2008, pp. 111-112) confirms that co-teaching models must be followed sequentially including: first, "One teaching-One assisting"; second, "Alternative teaching"; third, "Station teaching"; and finally, moving to "Team teaching", Therefore, co-teachers should take into consideration and examine all the different factors critically of these models before implementing one or more of them. To sum up, this research discussed a set of difficulties and factors related to co-teaching in the context of Chinese primary school between (NETs) and (NNETs), these factors including the effective collaboration between the two categories to provide a successful classroom and improve the level of student performance. Despite all the obstacles faced by Chinese schools, including the increasing number of native English speakers, co-teaching will remain a necessary process that must be taken into consideration in Chinese primary schools (2008, p. 115).

Collaboration in the Algerian Context

In recent years, following Algeria's independence in 1962, policymakers' main goal was to reform the educational system and implement a set of policies including the Arabization policy. This significant initiative aimed to change the French language to Arabic, in this context, Gherzouli and Dabaghine (2019, pp. 32-33) discussed the challenges in implementing the Arabization policy in the field of education according to what the law mentioned (law N° 64-230 of August 10, 1964): These challenges included the lack of trained teachers; moreover, a shortage of instructional materials. For instance, the ministry employed 31,000 teachers from both inside and outside the country. Additionally, the president established 30 normal schools to train teachers, thereby enhancing the quality of education nationwide.

The evidence presented before confirms that, despite all the efforts made by Algeria, Arabization has negatively impacted co-operation among teachers through: the imbalance between expatriate teachers and those who trained in French and Arabic which makes the co-operation a complex process, moreover, the lack of educational materials such as textbooks, which constitutes a major obstacle to sharing teaching tools among themselves, in addition to training teachers: specifically insufficient time for their training and their lack of understanding of the new pattern represented in their learning of a new language, which makes it difficult to work among themselves and thus affects the management of their classroom.

In the same context, Algerian universities are facing the same issue, concerning the lack of collaboration among university teachers. However, Dudley-Evans and St John (1998 as cited in Almagro & Carlos Vallego 2002, p. 10) based on three progressive stages of collaboration, especially in the field of the role of collaborator with ESP teachers, including cooperation, collaboration, and team teaching. The first stage is when the ESP teacher inquires about the different subjects in which the student participates besides defining the tasks for their target situation. Simultaneously, collaboration means the benefits of both teachers from each other's competence and experience through the integration of mutual interest to exchange their views aiming to improve the student's performance.

Theoretical Framework of Teacher Collaboration

This section explains the two most important theories in the teaching process, the theory of social constructivism and the theory of Communities of Practice (CoP), which are considered the theoretical focus in the field of teacher collaboration. These two theories shed light on the interaction and interaction of teachers and how they construct knowledge with each other.

Social Constructivism

Social constructivism is a learning theory proposed by Lev Vygotsky in 1968. It emphasises the importance of language and culture as two basic axes that play a role in a person's understanding of reality and communication with others. Through the cultural context and shared experience, the transition of language leads to learning concepts which are clarified and understood, language also shapes their perception of their environment and affects their mental development. Thus, Knowledge develops and is achieved through people who share a single culture and language with the collaboration as a whole (Deeba, Zakariya& Mohammed 2021, P. 406).

As the previous research conducted by Lui (2008, pp. 106-107) in Chinese primary schools about co-teaching approaches between (NETs) and (NNETs) in classroom, the study explores its relationship with the social constructivism represented in:

That the (NETs) benefit their students by understanding the language and its contextual meaning, in addition to their pronunciation and grammar skills, as native speakers of English, unlike (NNETs), despite the difficulties they face in learning English as a second language, and their role in providing advice and experiences to learners, as they have gone through the same stages of experiences in learning the language. This is known as cultural exchange with learners. Moreover, the co-teaching model conforms with the theory of social constructivism through the collaboration of (NETs) and (NNETs) by unifying and coordinating cultural and linguistic knowledge. This cooperation helps improve the learner's performance in terms of developing the four language skills in addition to grammar, vocabulary, and understanding the cultural context related to the language.

Communities of Practice (CoP)

Communities of practice are a collective process consisting of a group of people who share a common goal, which is to exchange opinions and knowledge in a specific field. Wenger,

McDermott & Snyder (2002, p. 4) present CoPs as “groups of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis” (as cited in Sánchez- Cardona, et al., 2012, p. 1821).

This illustrates the role of CoPs and their ongoing support in improving teaching skills among their practitioners based on competence and knowledge, for instance: in the context of CoPs, (NETs) and (NNETs) in Chinese primary schools work together through Scaffolding such as: (NETs) supporting (NNETs) in their English language proficiency especially when they face challenges in learning the language and working together as groups to exchange views and experiences to improve teaching skills, all of these strategies contribute to strengthening and developing student performance.

To sum up, this section presents two theories: social constructivism theory and CoP theory. Social constructivism theory in the learning process focuses on knowledge and cultural context and how teachers benefit from each other, while CoP theory discusses support and the efforts made by teachers in creating a supportive environment for learners.

Benefits of Teacher Collaboration

Collaborative teaching plays a crucial role in improving both teachers’ personal and professional development on the one hand and learners' achievements on the other hand. Teachers’ collaboration practices have a large number of positive outcomes. In the following outcomes and benefits, three levels will be determined: teacher level, student level, and school level.

Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the Teacher Level

All teachers have areas of need related to their teaching practices, regardless of their backgrounds and educational qualifications (Grandall et al., 2008 as cited in Celce-Murcia,

Brinton, & Snow, 2014, p. 631). Research strongly suggests that collaboration is a highly effective strategy for improving and enhancing teaching practices. Through engaging in collaborative efforts, teachers have the opportunity to promote interaction among teachers and prevent isolation, teachers who collaborate are more motivated and engaged compared to teachers, who don't collaborate (Nina Kolley, 2019, p. 11).

Furthermore, through collaborative practices, teachers can exchange ideas, strategies, competencies, and innovative teaching methods, they can share valuable resources and materials and align their pedagogical visions. This exchange is particularly beneficial for novice teachers with less experience who can gain invaluable insights from experienced ones to improve their teaching effectiveness. In addition to the previous, ideas that are the product of collaborative exchange appear to give rise to greater experimentation in classrooms, greater teacher learning and certainty, and lead to better problem solving solutions (Rosenholtz et al., 1985). Cochran-Smith (1999) and Lytle (2009) go beyond that when stating that teachers sharing experiences and working together in networks were better able to pose problems, identify inconsistencies between theories and practices, and challenge common routine in teaching practices.

However, it is important to recognise that even experienced teachers with more years of experience can significantly benefit from collaborative practices. As highlighted by Celce-Murcia et al. (2014), "If you are an experienced teacher, you probably have different needs and interests than someone just starting out in the profession" (p. 631).

Despite their extensive knowledge and experience, experienced teachers can also learn new approaches and strategies from their less experienced peers. Novice teachers often bring fresh perspectives, innovative ideas, and a deeper understanding of contemporary educational practices and technologies. Novice teachers may possess a greater familiarity with integrating ICTs and their pedagogical applications. By collaborating with experienced teachers, they can

guide them in integrating these technologies into their instructional practices. This collaborative process not only benefits experienced teachers but also provides novice teachers with valuable opportunities to refine their leadership and mentorship skills.

Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the School Level

The ability to work collaboratively with others is becoming an essential component of school development and effectiveness. Successful schools are measured by learners' academic achievement and are characterised by a high level of collaboration and teachers' collegiality. (Chapman and Muijs, 2013)

Caldwell and Spinks (1992) describe the worldwide move toward self-managing schools as a major trend in education. Currently, school administrators have significant authority in managing and overseeing their institutions in ways they believe will best contribute to their success. Each administrator endeavours to develop policies that address the challenges they encounter or align with the goals they seek to achieve. However, while there still is “governmental control”, there is freedom concerning the specific implementation of related tasks (Fullan, 2000) and (Ewald Kiel, 2020). Collaboration among teachers in its different forms can result in various beneficial aspects that are also found in processes of school development and that are equal indicators of effective schools (Doppenberg, den Brok & Bakx, 2012)

School effectiveness is related to many factors, and teachers are one of these factors. McKinsey's (2007) recent study on the world's best-performing school systems, confirms the importance of the teacher and claims that the only way to improve outcomes is to improve instruction. Teachers' personal development through collaboration is considered a way of improving instruction. Ballantyne, Sanderman and Levy (2008) and Darlin-Hammonds et al. (2008) claim that educational institutions that align their performance goals to teachers' professional development through professional learning communities (i.e. groups of teachers

who meet regularly to interact, plan, solve problems and learn together), those schools achieve positive outcomes. Moreover, fostering a strong sense of professional community (Louis et al., 1996)

Benefits of Teacher Collaboration at the Student Level

Establishing an effective school with collaborative practices among teachers to refine instruction is not for the sake of doing it, but all these are for the sake of improving students' outcomes and achievement. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2009), high-quality professional development (as a result of collaborative practices) is that which improves teachers' knowledge and instructional practices as well as accelerates students' learning. Teachers have to utilise a variety of methods that they can learn from one another to enhance and promote students' learning and attain better results. They can even talk about their students' challenges to get various perspectives, particularly from educators who have dealt with those issues in their early teaching careers.

Teachers can establish a shared view of what defines quality work and what instructional strategies are effective by analysing student work together. As teachers learn to define, discuss, and modify their methods in accordance with a widely accepted norm of teaching excellence, change will take place (Darling-Hammond and Richardson, 2009).

Collaborating on all aspects of teaching including planning, decision making and problem-solving leads to a shared collective responsibility for the outcomes (Killion, 2012). The focus shifts from individual learning goals to contributing to the learning and knowledge base of colleagues and the school (Cole, 2012).

According to the study of Goddard, Goddard and Tschannen-Moran (2007), there is a link between teacher collaboration and students' achievements. In other words, as the teachers improve teaching skills and knowledge, they begin to influence classroom instructions which

leads to better student outcomes. Cohen & Hill, (1998) and Kennedy, (2016) suggest that student achievement will not improve without making the necessary changes in teachers' classroom practices and these pedagogical transformations are unlikely to occur without effective teachers' engagement in collaborative behaviours.

Achievement Teams as a Collaborative Practice

It turns out that it is a must that teachers share their experiences, knowledge, resources and materials, perspectives, and strategies to improve students' outcomes. This is precisely why teamwork is seen as an essential way to implement collaborative practice in schools.

However, teams often form organically. The size of teams and the participants of those teams are controlled by school size, subject areas and grade levels, teachers' attitudes, and other factors. Even though these factors influence team composition, it remains a joint responsibility for everyone to build those teams in an effective way that enhances educational practices and promotes students' achievement and outcomes.

According to (Steve Ventura & Michelle Ventura, 2022), there are three common models of team formation:

Horizontal Teams

Forming horizontal teams (As presented in Figure 1.1) is possibly the most common method for bringing teachers together because these teams typically consist of teachers from the same grade level and content area.

Horizontal team teachers share the same goals and purpose besides they develop and administer common formative assessments, take actions and change their focus based on the results of the formative assessment and the evidence they have collected. This focus can target a subject area where the team can concentrate their efforts on improving instruction in that area or an identified student population, as a reaction the team can develop strategies to support these students more effectively. Sometimes, the focus is even on the difficulty level of the questions,

team can develop a schoolwide focus on strengthening effective teaching strategies, creating a shared vocabulary, and providing support structures for students to successfully move from one grade level to the next. Even more compelling are vertical teams' opportunities to cross-reference horizontal work and continue to recognise and close gaps in schoolwide learning. This supports all teachers working toward a schoolwide goal and gives them a common language and focus.

Figure 1.3: Vertical ELA Achievement Team.

Source: from *Achievement Teams: How a Better Approach to PLCs Can Improve Student Outcomes and Teacher Efficacy* (p. 20), by S. Ventura & M. Ventura, 2022, Corwin. Copyright 2022 by Corwin Press.

Specialist and Elective Teams

Specialist and elective teams consist of specialist teachers who have a single content area, such as English, Mathematics, Science and Elective teachers who have a single prep like Physical Education, Music or Drama.

Barriers Restricting Teacher Collaboration

Teacher collaboration is commonly recognised as an essential factor in enhancing instructional practices and improving student learning outcomes. However, numerous barriers and challenges can hinder effective collaboration among teachers. These obstacles can be categorised into structural, interpersonal, and cultural barriers.

Structural Barriers

Structural barriers include external factors that may weaken or even prevent collaborative practices among teachers, and lack of time was determined to be one of the strongest barriers to collaborative work. Teachers mostly have busy schedules filled with instructional duties, such as lesson preparation, grading and administrative responsibilities, leaving little room for collaborative activities (Lortie, 1975, p.179).

The absence of allocated collaboration time within the school schedule further exacerbates this issue, since most schools don't allot time for collaboration (Shakenova, 2017, p.39). Another critical obstacle is the lack of administrative support, if school leaders do not actively encourage collaboration, provide training, or set expectations for teamwork, teachers may see collaboration as optional or unimportant). Another issue is that many schools lack the appropriate physical spaces for collaborative practices. However, the physical arrangement of schools, including shared workspaces, staff rooms and meeting areas, can influence teacher collaboration and enhance its effectiveness.

Interpersonal Barriers

Interpersonal barriers refer to obstacles that arise from personal relationships and social dynamics among teachers. Social interactions play a fundamental role in cognitive development, as Vygotsky asserted. However, in the context of teacher collaboration, it requires mutual respect and trust, which can be hindered by personality differences or past conflicts

among teachers (Little, 1990). Moreover, fear of revealing individuals' weaknesses and mistakes leads to a feeling of vulnerability-based trust.

If teachers are to work collaboratively to clarify the essential learning for their courses and grade levels, write common assessments, and jointly analyse the results, they must overcome the fear that they may be exposed to their colleagues and principals as ineffective.

(DuFour et al., 2016, p.120)

Another interpersonal barrier is unequal participation, which can cause frustration and disengagement, weakening the effectiveness of collaboration, in some collaborative practices, some teachers may dominate discussions while others remain passive, Schnathorst (2009) claims that "Collaboration requires interactions between colleagues that is equally valued as well has equal power in making decisions."

Additionally, the lack of open communication can lead to misunderstandings and unwillingness to work together (Goddard et al., 2007). Lasonde and Israel (2009) highlight that effective teacher collaboration relies heavily on clear and open communication, which fosters trust and enhances the overall success of professional learning communities. In addition, some teachers may be resistant to collaboration due to ingrained habits, personal teaching preferences, or fear of change. A lack of trust among colleagues can also lead to resistance, teachers may feel uncomfortable with collaboration and more comfortable with a traditional model of teaching, DuFour et al. (2016, p. 120) state that "teachers who believe it is their job to teach and the students' job to learn, who are convinced that learning is a function of the student's aptitude rather than the teacher's expertise [...]".

Cultural Barriers

Schools often operate in isolation, with little collaboration among teachers, and sometimes even in direct competition. Teachers are mostly aware of the challenges in their

schools and have valuable insights into how teaching and learning could be improved. However, many do not feel comfortable taking the first step, fearing that their concerns will not be welcomed or that change is unlikely. Additionally, school cultures often reward individual accomplishments over teamwork, which can discourage collaboration among teachers.

School culture is important to the success of teacher collaboration and administrators can have an impact on school culture, effective school leadership plays a crucial role in fostering a culture of collaboration (Honigsfeld & Dove, 2010, p. 280). Kohm and Nance (2009) claim that “principals can foster a school environment that leads to collaboration and teacher leadership by sharing responsibility with teachers as often as possible and by helping them develop skills that foster collaborative problem solving” (p.67).

In addition, teachers may not have sufficient training or experience in effective collaborative practices. Professional development programs often focus on instructional methods rather than teamwork skills, leaving teachers unprepared for meaningful collaboration., according to Kohm and Nance (2009), collaborative practices culture are guided by two factors, transparency, which means that a minimum of work is done behind closed doors and the second factor is shared decision making.

Conclusion

As a final point, this introductory chapter presents the importance of collaboration among teachers in different educational stages. The chapter, through a review of the literature, addresses the various basic concepts of collaboration based on the different points of view of educational scholars, the history, theoretical foundations, and benefits of cooperative teaching, as well as teaching teams. It also presents a comprehensive analysis of the most important barriers and reasons that hinder the teaching process, classified into three sections “structural barriers, interpersonal barriers and cultural barriers”.

In general, this chapter highlights the importance of collaboration as the key to the success of any pedagogical institution, through improving teamwork techniques and the necessity of working among teams in all its forms, which contributes to creating a stimulating atmosphere to strengthen the relationship and foster communication and experiences among teachers.

CHAPTER TWO:
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Chapter Two: Research Methodology

Introduction	29
Objective of The Study.....	30
Research Questions.....	30
Hypotheses.....	30
Research design	31
Research Methodology	32
Case Study	32
Description of Setting	33
Sampling.....	35
Population of the study	36
Piloting.....	36
Research Tools	37
Questionnaire	37
Interview	40
Data Analysis Methods.....	41
Quantitative Data Analysis	42
Qualitative Data Analysis	42
Conclusion.....	43

Research Methodology

Introduction

Teaching English at all levels and mainly at the university level has become a key concern for the Algerian government and decision-makers. Various studies have been conducted on the different factors that could enhance the teaching and learning of the English language in our country. Among these factors, teacher collaboration stands out as a crucial element, and it is increasingly being emphasised even in English-speaking countries. As English students, we chose to focus our study on this particular aspect, believing it plays an important role in improving the process of English language teaching/learning. This growing interest in English is not incidental. Over the years, it has gradually become the preferred foreign language, particularly in higher education and scientific fields, where it is often seen as more practical than French. This shift was even highlighted in a headline from an Algerian daily on 17 September 2010: *"English gives French a rough ride at the university!"* (Semmar, 2010, as cited in Benrabah, 2014).

While the previous chapter tackled the review of the related literature, the current chapter is devoted to outlining the research methodology adopted for this study. It highlights the research questions and hypotheses guiding the study. Furthermore, it describes the adopted research design, the target population, and the setting in which the study was conducted. In addition, it explains the data collection tools (questionnaire and interview) and procedures, as well as the methods employed for data analysis. This chapter sheds light on the practical investigation of the EFL teachers' attitudes toward Teacher Collaboration and explores the barriers that may hinder such collaboration in the English Department at the University of Mascara.

Objective of The Study

The objective of this research is to determine the extent to which teachers engage in collaborative practices within the Department of English at the University of Mustapha Stambouli in Mascara. Second, to explore essential barriers that prevent collaboration among teachers, if they do exist. Furthermore, this study seeks to open a broad and advanced scope in the field of education regarding the possibility of promoting teacher collaboration in order to achieve a highly efficient educational system in the future.

Research Questions

This study seeks to address the following questions:

- 1) To what extent do teachers in the English Department at Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara engage in collaborative practices?

This research aims to study the level of teacher collaboration, whether it is frequent, occasional, or rare, through qualitative and quantitative instruments.

- 2) What are the main barriers that hinder collaboration among teachers in the English Department?

This research seeks to discover and analyse the most important reasons and concerns that prevent teachers from collaborating. Given the different opinions, we are dedicated to providing a comprehensive understanding of these concerns and challenges, which are among the most prominent problems facing educational institutions.

Hypotheses

Therefore, the following hypotheses are formulated

- 1) EFL University teachers collaborate to a limited extent.

This hypothesis addresses the level of collaboration among teachers and whether there is coordination in the English Department among teachers.

- 2) EFL University Teachers' ability to collaborate is negatively influenced by structural barriers (such as time constraints and workload), cultural barriers (such as differing pedagogical beliefs and resistance to change), and interpersonal barriers (such as personality differences and lack of trust).

According to several studies, Lortie (1975), Little (1990) and Schnathorst (2009), there are several barriers and fundamental concerns that prevent collaboration among teacher's including structural obstacles such as time constraints and workload, which negatively affect teachers' ability to collaborate, as well as cultural barriers and interpersonal barriers, including different pedagogical beliefs, resistance to change, personality differences and lack of trust.

Research design

To conduct a study in educational research, the research design is one of the basic steps followed by the researcher, as it is one of the strategies that facilitate the research process regarding its objectives and the process of analysing its data, Kumar (2011) defines research design as "a procedural plan that is adopted by the researcher to answer questions validly, objectively, accurately and economically" (p. 345).

In general, the research design in the study is the comprehensive plan, while the methodology is the strategies and processes used to conduct the research (Creswell, 2009) to study a specific topic. The design must be chosen based on several reasons, such as the research issue, the nature of the problem, the personal experiences of the researcher and the target audience.

The overall decision involves which design should be used to study a topic.

Informing this decision should be the worldview assumptions the researcher

brings to the study; procedures of inquiry (called strategies); and specific methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

(Creswell, 2009, p22)

Research Methodology

Mixed methods research is one of the methods used by researchers in their studies to answer the research questions. Mixed methods research combines both qualitative and quantitative research tools in one study. In other words, research using different methods is known to achieve reliable and credible results by combining and collecting qualitative and quantitative data, and given the diverse opinions, it helps and facilitates the understanding process for researchers. (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011, as cited in Cohen et Al, 2018, p 32)

Case Study

A case study is a detailed and in-depth study of a particular topic with the aim of providing comprehensive details in a specific context. Yin (1994) described the case study as “an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident ... and relies on multiple sources of evidence.” (p. 13)

Collaboration is an important factor in enhancing student outcomes. In order to understand the different perspectives of teachers on the subject of collaboration among themselves in the English department, a case study helps us to see the level of collaboration in the department and also explore and evaluate teachers' opinions on how and why these difficulties prevent the process of collaboration among themselves, according to Kumar (2011), “The case study, though dominantly a qualitative study design, is also prevalent in quantitative research. A case could be an individual, a group, a community, an instance, an episode, an event,

a subgroup of a population, a town or a city. To be called a case study, it is important to treat the total study population as one entity” (p. 123).

Description of Setting

The study was conducted at the University of Mustapha Stambouli, which was established in Mascara in 1986 divided into 07 faculties: “The faculty of science and technology, The faculty of exact science, science of nature and life, law and political science, economics business and management sciences, humanities and social sciences”. Among these is the faculty of letters and languages, with the Department of English Language and Literature, established in 2002. The department operates on the LMD system. First, at the undergraduate level, learners study for three consecutive years to obtain a bachelor’s degree. Second, at the postgraduate level, learners can study their desired specialisation to obtain a master’s degree over a period of two years. After graduation, they can continue their postgraduate studies PHD.

Figure 2.1: Faculties of Mustapha Stambouli University

The English Department was chosen as a suitable location to study English teachers' attitudes towards Teacher Collaboration, as they are highly qualified and have relationships with specialised professors at national and foreign universities, which allows them to exchange knowledge with them and keep informed of all the latest developments in the English Department. All these factors contribute to exploring the barriers and obstacles that prevent collaboration among teachers.

Table 2.1: Levels, Specialisations and Grades in The Department of English at Mustapha Stambouli University

Levels	Specialisations	Grades
Undergraduate (Bachelor's Degree)	English Language	<i>L1 (L= Licence)</i>
		<i>L2</i>
		<i>L3</i>
	Translation	<i>L1</i>
		<i>L2</i>
Postgraduate (Master's Degree)	Didactics	<i>M1</i>
		<i>M2</i>
	Civilization	<i>M1</i>
		<i>M2</i>
	ESP	<i>M1</i>
		<i>M2</i>
	ESP for Tourism	<i>M1</i>

Sampling

Sampling is a technique used to study a population by selecting a specific group, enabling the researcher to collect the largest possible amount of data and analyse it accurately. Kumar (2011) defines sampling as “the process of selecting a few (a sample) from a bigger group (the population) to become the basis for estimating or predicting the prevalence of an unknown piece of information, situation or outcome regarding the bigger group” (p. 177). He further adds that “a sample is a subgroup of the population you are interested in”.

There are many strategies and types of sampling, each varying from one to another. Purposive sampling was used in this study, based on the shared knowledge and experiences of teachers regarding the collaborative process in the Department of English.

Population of the study

In the department of English for the academic year 2024/2025, the population of the study consists of 60 EFL teachers as presented in **Table 3.1**, teaching different modules at both levels, undergraduate (Licence) and postgraduate (Master). The population consists of both male and female participants, including experienced and novice teachers.

Piloting

The pilot study is an important step in conducting research. It is a small study used to collect data, it also provides an opportunity for researchers to gain an overview of their research and explore the most significant weaknesses in the research design.

In other words, a pilot study is a small-scale study whose purpose is to verify the effectiveness and reliability of research tools, and it also examines whether the research can be applied or not, and also ensures that more effective and accurate feedback and results are provided in the research design. (Arain et Al., 2010 as cited in Lowe, 2019, 117).

In general, a survey was conducted with some teachers in the Department of English at the University of Mascara, to answer some questions from their responses, it became clear that they faced some difficulties in answering the questionnaire, which negatively reflected the quality of data. In order to evaluate the validity of the questionnaire, the most appropriate solution was to reduce the number of open-ended questions to ensure complete and correct reliability and make the questionnaire easier and quicker to complete.

To sum up, piloting the questionnaire is primp to ensure the effectiveness and success of the data collection process in research. Moreover, it saves effort and time, provides an opportunity for comparison between diverse groups, and facilitates all difficulties and careful examination of the validity of the question.

Research Tools

In this research, both qualitative, through interviews, and quantitative, through questionnaires, methods are employed to address the research questions and validate the hypotheses. The quantitative approach is used to examine and quantify the extent of collaboration among teachers in the English department, while the qualitative method is adopted to explore the barriers encountered by EFL teachers in the department that hinder their collaboration.

To conduct any research, several research tools should be used to reach the study's aim. These tools are generally defined as different ways that the researchers use to obtain data for the investigation thereby this research will employ different tools including: a structured questionnaire for EFL university teachers enrolled in the department of English language at the University of Mustapha Stambouli in the city of Mascara, as well as interviews conducted with other EFL university teachers from the same department. Each method serves to gather valuable insights from different perspectives on the topic.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire is a systematic and essential tool for collecting first-hand data from the target population, particularly within theoretically grounded research. It is especially relevant and widely used in educational research contexts. It allows researchers to get numerical data from a large population in a relatively short period.

The present questionnaire explores the perspectives of twenty-seven (27) university teachers on the extent of their collaboration practices in teaching in the English department. It also elicits the different barriers teachers may encounter, which may prevent them from collaboration. In addition, it investigates the beliefs of the teachers about the importance of collaboration at the three levels: teachers' level, students' level and the school (university) level.

In the current context, the questionnaire is composed of four (04) sections and consists of twenty-two (22) questions (See Appendices), varying in its structure between closed-ended and open-ended questions. Closed-ended questions, such as Likert scale and yes/no questions, are salutary because they make the questionnaire easier and quicker to complete, and they are quicker to code and analyse (Bailey, 1994, p. 118). On the other hand, open-ended questions are advantageous in collecting in-depth and supplementary information that enhances the overall understanding of participants' perspectives that may not be captured through closed-ended questions, especially when the range of possible responses is not enough or not very expressive to participants. In this research, the majority of the questions in the questionnaire are closed-ended, which was done intentionally to ensure consistency in responses, facilitate quantitative analysis, and make the gathered data easier to compare and interpret. guide the students and avoid them feeling overwhelmed by the potential responses. As it is mentioned before, this questionnaire is divided into four (04) sections and focuses on the extent of teacher collaboration in the department, challenges that teachers may encounter which hinder teacher collaboration and finally, teachers' beliefs about the importance and benefits of teacher collaboration, and the questions are grouped accordingly.

Section One: Teachers' Profile and Personal Information, (questions 1-5) aims to collect basic demographic and professional information from the participants. It includes questions about gender, years of experience, and the modules and levels teachers are in charge of. This information helps provide a profile of the participants.

Section Two: Teachers' Collaboration Frequency, (questions 6-14), the questionnaire examines the frequency of collaboration among teachers using a Likert scale. Respondents are asked to rate their collaboration practices on a scale from "Always" to "Never" across various scenarios, such as collaborating with colleagues from the same department, specialisation, or teaching similar modules. Additionally, it explores whether teachers engage in activities like

lesson planning, discussing teaching methods, peer observation, or co-teaching. This section aims to assess the extent to which teachers engage in collaborative practices.

Section Three: Teacher Collaboration Barriers and Challenges, (questions 15-17) addresses the obstacles and challenges that teachers may face when trying to collaborate with their colleagues. The respondents are asked to identify the main barriers to effective collaboration, such as time constraints, lack of administrative support, differences in teaching philosophies, and limited physical spaces for collaboration. An open-ended option is provided to allow participants to mention additional obstacles not listed. This section helps to understand the different factors that may hinder collaboration among teachers.

Section Four: Teachers' Beliefs and Teacher Collaboration Benefits, (questions 18-22) focuses on teachers' beliefs and attitudes towards the benefits of collaboration. It includes a series of yes/no questions to explore whether teachers believe teacher collaboration contributes to professional development, improves teaching quality, enhances student outcomes, and fosters a positive work environment. The section also includes a question about whether teachers would be ready to participate in collaborative practices if given the opportunity and the right conditions. This section aims to estimate teachers' perceptions of the importance and value of collaboration in the academic environment.

Teachers' Profile. A total of (25) EFL teachers from the Department of English Language at the University of Mustapha Stambouli were selected randomly to participate in the questionnaire. These teachers represent a diverse range of specialisations, with varying years of experience, and are responsible for teaching different modules and levels within the department. The questionnaire was administered both online using Google Forms via Gmail and in person to gauge the extent of teacher collaboration within the Department of English and to provide insights into the collaboration practices and challenges faced by teachers, as well as their beliefs about the importance of collaborative efforts in the academic environment.

Interview

The interviews are research tools widely used to help the researcher understand and explore the research behaviours and phenomena. Using an interview as an addition to the questionnaire can be more insightful and lead to more accurate, detailed and in-depth data, Hochschild (2009) notes that the interview can do what surveys cannot, which is to investigate issues in depth, to see how and why people shape their ideas in the ways that they do, how and why they make connections between ideas, values, events, opinions, and behaviours. There are three well-known types of interviews, namely: structured, unstructured, and semi-structured. The interview can be a positive addition to any research because it increases the knowledge of both the interviewer and the interviewee. Furthermore, it enhances mutual understanding and cooperation. However, the researchers are still facing some limitations in the interview process, since it can be time-consuming.

To address the second research question, a face-to-face interview was carried out as a second significant instrument. The interview was administered to seven (07) EFL teachers who were not a part of the questionnaire and were selected based on a number of variables, including their years of teaching experience at Mascara University, the specialisations they are responsible for and the modules they teach and their additional administrative duties. The sample included two (02) experienced teachers, two (02) other teachers with only a few years of experience, two (02) teachers responsible for teaching the same module at the level of the department and one (01) teacher who combines both teaching responsibilities and administrative duties within the department. Each one was interviewed alone. The type of interview used in this investigation is semi-structured, offering great flexibility in the interaction. Most of the questions were open-ended questions to encourage the participants to express themselves freely and provide in-depth responses, as Stehr-Green et al. (2003) claim

that “Open-ended questions allow the respondent to express his/her perspectives about a subject and are useful in characterising attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours.” (p. 3).

Before starting, the meeting was opened with a concise introduction in which the topic was defined and the major points which are going to be discussed were identified by the researchers. Additionally, the researchers asked for permission to record the session, and guaranteed confidentiality to the interviewees. The reasons behind designing the second tool are: Firstly, researchers wanted to reinforce their collected data regarding the frequency of collaboration in the department. Secondly, while the second section of the questionnaire which addressed to the challenges and barriers that hinder collaboration through a multiple-choice question which doesn't allow the researchers to have a deeper insight about the real reasons that prevent teachers from collaboration. Therefore, it became necessary to administer a second tool which will help to gather in-depth data about the barriers and challenges which may hinder Teacher collaboration.

The interview consists of 3 sections, the first section titled: Teachers' Background and Experiences with Teacher Collaboration includes three (03) questions about the respondents' years of experience at the university, as well as their experience with Teacher collaboration in the Department of English, the second section contains two (02) questions about teachers' beliefs on the importance of Teacher Collaboration for their personal development and the enhancement of students outcomes and achievements, and the third section with eight (08) questions about the barriers and challenges that may hinder Teacher Collaboration, in addition to extra questions were asked to specific teachers based on the variables they were selected for.

Data Analysis Methods

Once the data is gathered, the next step is to analyse the findings systematically and formally to extract useful information for further interpretation. Data analysis is a crucial

methodological step in research, as it allows researchers to obtain valuable insights that support informed judgments. To ensure the reliability and validity of the results, the researchers used a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative analyses to enhance the depth and richness of the findings. Accordingly, the qualitative and quantitative data are analysed separately during the analytical step. The analysis followed a QUAN → Qual sequence, as suggested by Morse (1991) (Ary et al., 2010).

Quantitative Data Analysis

In the present research, a quantitative methodology is used to analyse the data gathered through the teachers' questionnaires. This approach involves the use of descriptive statistical methods, such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, to summarise and interpret the numerical data. These techniques allow the researcher to provide a clear overview of the collected data.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Analysing qualitative data involves examining and interpreting non-numerical information to gain insights into the beliefs, opinions, perspectives, and subjective experiences of individuals, groups, or communities. Ary et al. (2010) asserted that qualitative analysis is "an attempt to comprehend the phenomenon under study, synthesise information and explain relationships, theorise about how and why the relationships appear as they do, and reconnect the new knowledge with what is already known" (p. 481). This was realised through the use of the interview with EFL teachers.

In this context, Patton (2002, as cited in Cohen, 2018) remarks, "though qualitative data analysis turns data into findings, there is no simple formula or recipe for this" (p. 432). There is no single or correct way to analyse and present qualitative data, it should align with the desired objectives. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) further explain that qualitative data

analysis is a complex process. In this study, the researchers followed stages provided by Ary et al. (2010, P. 482): 1) Organising and familiarising 2) Coding and reducing 3) Interpreting and representing, which is realised in the study by selecting informants' responses. Reading and listening to responses that aim at representing the unit of meaning of responses under identical views. After identifying themes or identical views, the researcher followed the coding phase, which included the identification of categories and themes. Later on, these data were reported and displayed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter was concerned with the framework of the research process. In addition to the description of the sample under study, which consists of university EFL teachers, the setting of the study was conducted in the Department of English Language at Mostafa Stambouli University. It also details the data collection tools used for testing the research hypotheses. A questionnaire was employed to collect quantitative data related to the first hypothesis, whereas an interview was conducted to gather qualitative data to test the second hypothesis. Furthermore, this chapter discusses the methods used to analyse the collected data, highlighting how both quantitative and qualitative methods were brought together to provide an in-depth understanding of the topic under investigation. Overall, this chapter paves the way for the next, which will present and interpret the key findings that emerged from analysing the collected data.

CHAPTER THREE:
DATA ANALYSIS

Chapter Three: Data Analysis

Introduction	46
Data Analysis Tools.....	46
Questionnaire Analysis and Interpretations	46
Interview Analysis and Interpretations	56
Discussion.....	64
Limitations.....	70
Recommendations	71
Conclusion.....	74

Data Analysis

Introduction

This chapter tackles the practical part of the study which was data analysis and findings interpretations of the data that was collected through two different data collection tools: questionnaires and interviews with EFL university teachers to answer the research questions. This chapter also focused on the most important difficulties and challenges that hinder the process of collaboration among the EFL university teachers in the Department of English. In view of the results reached and in order to provide a complete version, this research seeks to provide some recommendations to promote teamworking and encourage for collaborative efforts for the benefit of both teachers and students, as they are the target group within the framework of the collaborative partnership.

Data Analysis Tools

In an effort to analyse the collected data, the researchers presented the information in four different forms, including tables, pie charts, bar graphs and notes. These varied methods are necessary to illustrate and analyse both quantitative and qualitative data, enabling researchers to draw meaningful conclusions.

Questionnaire Analysis and Interpretations

The researchers have administered a questionnaire to twenty-five (25) EFL university teachers, as it was mentioned in Chapter Two (see page 37). It aimed to elicit data about the frequency of Teacher Collaboration at the level of the Department of English as its primary objective, represented in section two, in addition to three other sections related to teachers' profiles and personal information, the barriers that may hinder Teacher Collaboration and the importance of Teacher Collaboration.

Section One: Teachers' profile and personal information

Question 01: Teachers' Gender

Figure 3.1: Participants' Distribution According to their Gender.

As it was highlighted earlier, the questionnaire was administered to 25 participants, and the pie chart above shows that 60%, that is, 15 out of 25 of the participants, which is the majority of the sample, were females, while 40% that is, 10 out of 25 were males. This imbalance may influence the engagement of collaboration among teachers in the department, and therefore, a more balanced sampling in future studies is highly recommended.

Question 02: Years of Experience

Figure 3.2: Participants' Distribution According to their Years of Experience.

According to the results displayed in the previous table, it is shown that the majority of the participants 72 %, that is, 18 out of 25, teach English at the university for more than 05 years. While seven teachers only with a percentage of 18%, have less than 05 years of experience.

Question 03: What Levels Are You in Charge of?**Table 3.1:** Participants' Distribution According to the Level and Grades They Teach.

Levels	Grades	Number of teachers	Percentage
Undergraduate (19)	L1 (L= Licence)	10	40%
	L2	3	12%
	L3	6	24%
Postgraduate (22)	M1 (M= Master)	12	48%
	M2	10	40%

The table above illustrates that the sampling under study (25) teachers teach different grades at different levels, undergraduate and postgraduate. Most of the teachers who participated in this questionnaire are in charge of Master 1, with 48%, followed by M2 and L1, with 40% for each. This implies that the majority of teachers at the department are working with the same students throughout the whole school year.

Question 04: What Specialisation Are You in Charge of?**Table 3.2:** Participants' Distribution According to the Specialisations They Teach.

Specialisations	Number of teachers	Percentage
English Language (<i>Licence</i>)	10	40%
Didactics (<i>Master</i>)	08	32%
ESP (<i>Master</i>)	06	24%
ESP for Tourism (<i>Master</i>)	04	16%
Translation (<i>Licence</i>)	02	08%

The table presents the specialisations that the participants are in charge of. It shows that the participants of the questionnaire (25) are in charge of varied specialisations in the department, and the majority of teachers are responsible for more than one specialisation. The

findings indicate that a large number of teachers are assigned to the same students throughout the academic year.

Question 05: What Modules Are You Responsible for?

Table 3.3: Participants' Distribution According to the Modules They Teach.

Modules	Number of teachers
Research Methodology	4
Civilization	3
Oral Expression	3
ESP	3
Written Expression and Reading Comprehension	2
Curriculum Conception in ESP	2
Linguistics and Phonetics	2
Specialized Translation	2
Didactics	2
Assessment and Evaluation	2
Linguistics Phonetics	2
Study of Literary Texts	1
University Techniques & Tasks (TTU)	1
Psycholinguistics	1
Grammar	1
Research Tools	1

The table above presents the modules that the participants are in charge of. It shows that the participants of the questionnaire (25) are in charge of different modules for different grades, as mentioned before (see **Table 3.1**). The data shows that most modules are taught by more than one teacher. The most widely taught module is *Research Methodology* by four teachers, followed by *Civilisation*, *Oral expression* and *ESP* by 03 teachers, and 02 teachers are in charge of the 07 other modules. In contrast, several modules such as: *Study of literature texts*, *TTU*, *Psycholinguistics*, *Grammar* and *Research tools* are taught by only 01 teacher. The findings indicate that a large number of teachers are assigned different modules. Moreover, the data reveal that most modules taught by more than one teacher offer potential for collaboration among those responsible for them, particularly in areas such as syllabus design, lesson planning, and exam preparation and uniformity. In contrast, teachers who are solely in charge of specific

modules may prefer working in isolation. However, some modules share similar objectives and can complement each other in practice. For instance, *Research Tools* can be associated with *Research Methodology*, and *Grammar* can be contextualised with other modules, especially content-based ones such as *Civilisation* or *Literary Texts*.

Section Two: Teachers' Collaboration Frequency

Table 3.4: Teacher Collaboration Frequency in the Department.

Items	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Always
I collaborate with my colleagues from the same department.	20%	36%	24%	20%
I work with my colleagues from the same specialisation.	16%	36%	40%	8%
I work with my colleagues responsible for the same levels.	28%	36%	32%	4%
I work with my colleagues teaching the same modules.	24%	32%	44%	00%
I work only with one or two of my colleagues.	16%	28%	44%	12%
I engage with my colleagues in lesson planning.	44%	40%	16%	00%
I discuss teaching methods and strategies with my colleagues.	20%	36%	32%	12%
I participate in peer observation or co-teaching sessions.	56%	24%	16%	4%
I discuss my learners' achievements with my colleagues	16%	16%	56%	12%
<i>Average</i>	<i>24.44%</i>	<i>31.56%</i>	<i>33.78%</i>	<i>8.00%</i>

According to the table above, which represents the frequency of Teacher Collaboration in different forms and situations. Researchers will be able to answer the first research question about the frequency of teacher collaboration among EFL university teachers in the department of English at Mascara University. The table shows that the highest frequency was for “sometimes” with 33.78% of collaboration in all its forms and situations. In contrast, the lowest frequency was for “always” with 8%. “Rarely” and “Never” together with a total of 56% combined, indicating a limited extent of Teacher Collaboration.

Having a deeper close to the findings related to each situation or form of Teacher Collaboration in the presented table, it becomes clear that the majority of teacher with 88% answered for limited engagement in “lesson planning” as a collaborative practice while 56% of the teachers have chosen “Never” when asked about their participation in “peer observation or co-teaching sessions” as a form of teacher collaboration. In contrast, the researchers have noticed that the highest level of collaboration practices appears in the “discussion of learners’ achievements” with 66% for either always or sometimes.

Section Three: Teacher Collaboration Barriers and Challenges

Question 01: What are the main obstacles to teacher collaboration?

Figure 3.3: Obstacles and Challenges to Teacher Collaboration.

As a subsidiary objective of the questionnaire, this question aims to investigate the obstacles and challenges that may prevent EFL teachers in the Department of English from working collaboratively. The question was designed as a multiple-choice question (MCQ) combined with an open-ended question to offer more flexibility to teachers in expressing their perspectives. As is apparent from the graph above, time constraints were the most frequently chosen obstacle, with 18 responses, followed by personality differences, selected by 15

teachers, and differences in teaching philosophy and strategy, chosen by 14 teachers. Limited physical spaces came next, selected by 10 teachers, and 09 selections for both lack of trust and lack of administrative support. In response to the open-ended question on additional barriers, participants provided the following answers:

- “When you are alone to teach some modules for some levels”. The participant noted that being the only teacher who is responsible for a specific module can be a barrier to collaboration or even make it unnecessary, resulting in more isolated teaching.
- “I am a novice teacher, no one helps me, and no one talks to me”.
- “Overconfidence for some teachers combines with disregarding novice teachers’ levels”.
According to these participants' answers, the novice versus experienced teachers may be considered a serious challenge for teacher collaboration.
- “Some teachers find it challenging to engage in collaboration, as they subconsciously regard us as inferior due to our former status as their students.”. Another participant highlighted the novice and experienced teachers' relationship issue, along with the pride or ego of some experienced teachers, even if it's subconsciously, according to the participant's answer.
- “The mood in the department does not motivate to collaborate”. One participant referred to the 'department mood' as the overall emotional atmosphere within the department, which can influence how members are feeling, consequently leading to limited collaborative teaching practices."
- “No one cares, as collaboration is not imposed on teachers. I strongly believe that had the teachers been imposed to gather and talk, and collaborate, they would have enjoyed teaching and sharing experiences.”. This participant suggested that teacher collaboration should be imposed on university teachers by policymakers, and claims that once teachers start collaborating, they will enjoy sharing expertise.

Section Four: Teachers' Beliefs and Teacher Collaboration Benefits

Question 01: Do you believe that Teacher Collaboration is essential for professional development and improves teaching qualities?

Figure 3.4: Teachers' Beliefs on Teacher Collaboration and Professional Development.

The question aims to elicit participants' perceptions and beliefs about the importance of Teacher Collaboration in helping teachers improve their teaching skills, widen their knowledge and develop themselves professionally. According to the statistics gathered from participants, the vast majority agreed on Teacher Collaboration's importance in improving and enhancing their teaching qualities and developing them professionally, with only one participant with a contrary view.

Question 02: Do you believe that Teacher Collaboration enhances students' outcomes?

Figure 3.5: Teachers' Beliefs on Teacher Collaboration and Students' Outcomes.

As demonstrated on the pie chart above, the vast number of participants believe that Teacher Collaboration contributes in enhancing students' outcomes and promoting their achievement, while only one teacher has answered the question with "No", expressing his beliefs that Teacher Collaboration doesn't enhance students' outcomes. These findings show that the majority of university teachers are aware of the importance of Teacher Collaboration in enhancing their learners' achievements and outcomes. However, their collaborative initiatives are rarely put into practice.

Question 03: Do you believe that Teacher Collaboration is crucial for school (university) development and effectiveness?

Figure 3.6: Teachers' Beliefs on Teacher Collaboration and University Effectiveness.

The results displayed in the figure revealed that all 25 teachers agreed that teacher collaboration plays a crucial role in the development of the university and contributes to greater institutional effectiveness. These results reflect the high level of awareness among university teachers regarding the importance of Teacher Collaboration across different levels.

Question 04: Do you believe that Teacher Collaboration fosters a positive and supportive work environment?

Figure 3.7: Teachers' Beliefs on Teacher Collaboration and Work Environment.

The figure above demonstrates that all 25 teachers agreed that teacher collaboration fosters a positive and supportive work environment. Therefore, the results indicate that the vast majority of teachers may work in collaboration if given the chance.

Question 05: If given the opportunity and the right conditions, would you like to collaborate more with your colleagues?

Figure 3.8: Teachers' Readiness and Willingness to Collaborate.

This question aims to gauge teachers' readiness and willingness to engage in collaborative practices. As the results displayed above, in contrast to one teacher who answered "No", the vast majority of teachers expressed their total readiness and willingness to collaborate with their colleagues within the department, provided that the appropriate conditions and opportunities are available. This led to the second question, which was addressed in the interview: What are the barriers and obstacles that prevent the majority of willing and ready teachers from collaboration?

Interview Analysis and Interpretations

The purpose of this interview was to collect qualitative data on teachers' attitudes toward collaboration. The interview was carried out with a specific group of English language teachers

in the Department of English at the University of Mustapha Stambouli in Mascara, and given their academic experiences, the aim of conducting the interview was to study ideas and differing views on the most important challenges that prevent collaboration among them. The interview was divided into three sections with a total number of 13 questions as shown below:

Section One: Teacher's Background

This section is divided into three questions that aim to provide information about the length of time teachers have taught English and their experiences with collaboration.

Question one: How long have you been teaching English at the university?

The teachers' experience in teaching English ranged from 07 to 23 years in various specialisations and levels.

Question two: Have you participated in any form of collaboration? If yes, what are the teaching activities have you participated in as part of a team?

This question serves a subsidiary objective for the interview. It aimed to measure the frequency of collaboration among EFL teachers in the department of English as a reinforcement for the gathered data through the questionnaire. The majority of the teachers noted that they collaborated from their very beginning of teaching. According to Teacher (C), collaboration occurred only once during his career, and it was about agreeing on a unified curriculum among translation teachers, and he added that this collaboration was compelled by the Ministry of Higher Education. Another participant, Teacher (B) stated that collaboration occurred in an informal and friendly manner, with no formal or structured collaboration, and he said, "There was very little collaboration; some time ago, when I taught methodology to second-year students, we had to sit down and agree on certain terms. If you consider that collaboration, then yes.". Furthermore, they talked about administrative meetings related to administrative and structural affairs or sometimes corridor chats that don't last more than 5 minutes, while Others

highlighted that they do collaborate, but only with one colleague, who is often their former teacher or supervisor. Other teachers' responses were directly negative, as Teacher (F) mentioned, "I haven't participated in any type of clear collaboration with colleagues.". The findings of this question revealed that there is limited collaboration among teachers in the department of English; most of their collaborative practices were during the early stages of their careers or in a manner that benefits neither their personal growth nor impacts their students' outcomes.

Question three: Do you feel comfortable working in teams? Why or why not?

In fact, teamwork achieves fruitful results by strengthening communication, interaction, and creativity. It also contributes to revealing one's inner capabilities and working to fulfil one's desires and bring them to life. Among the various answers to this question, most of the teachers agree that they feel comfortable working in teams.

The interviewee (C) asserted that: "teamwork is highly productive, motivating, it creates a supportive social environment among teachers and allows for the enhancement of teaching strategies". In addition to the teacher (D) said: "Yes, I do, since it is a very stimulating and enriching experience.". Whereas some teachers, including the participant (B), believe that: "teamwork depends on the personal relationships among teachers, which means a lack of effective communication, such as differences in ideas and opinions as well as personal disputes, for instance, competition and work pressures, which hinder collaboration."

Section Two: Teacher Collaboration Importance

This section consisted of 02 questions. The purpose of this section is to focus on examining the value of collaboration in teachers' career advancement and how it is reflected in student outcomes.

Question one: Do you believe that teacher collaboration is important for your professional development? How?

Collaboration plays an important role in the teaching process as it motivates and strengthens teachers' skills and competence, fortifying their ability to continue and achieve successful results. The interviewee (E) commented that: "As a novice teacher, I benefited from attending classes with experienced teachers in order to identify shortcomings and discover my strengths and weaknesses in the teaching method". While the teacher (F) believes that: "collaborating with teachers increases autonomy and self-efficacy, as well as creates a supportive educational environment."

An alternative perspective was offered by the participant (D) who confirmed that: "teacher collaboration is sometimes essential for professional development since academic careers implicitly rely on it now, e.g., writing joint papers, participating in seminars, elaborating on projects, etc. however, I usually prefer working alone to keep myself concentrated on what I do far from others 'noisy data'."

Question Two: In your opinion, does teacher collaboration play an important role in enhancing student outcomes and promoting their achievements? If yes, how?

In the realm of education, a student's educational achievements can be improved through discussions and meetings among teachers to study the Academic differences of the student's behaviours and shortcomings and work on developing teaching techniques for what is best for the learner. The teacher (E) expressed that: "When we work together, we focus, for example, on the most significant weaknesses and deficiencies in the student's writing skills, which positively impacts the student's performance and improves their educational level." On the other hand, the Interviewee (F) stated: "Yes, sharing expertise, knowledge, and exchanging pedagogical ideas would allow teachers to avoid time and effort-consuming and focus more on

innovation and creativity, especially within the evolving landscape of education and AI revolution.”

Section Three: Teacher Collaboration Barriers

This part consisted of 08 questions. Through the interviews conducted, teachers mentioned the most important barriers that prevent the collaboration process.

Question one: Do you believe that teacher collaboration in the department can be hindered by certain barriers or obstacles? If yes, could you describe some of these challenges?

- **Distance and time constraints:** Time is a difficult issue for teachers to collaborate with each other, limiting opportunities for meetings and dialogue, in addition to the variety of responsibilities outside of work. The teacher (G) stated that:” Time constraints are a major factor as they limit the process of communication and meeting among us due to differences in work relationships and schedules.”
- **Differences in attitudes and teaching methods:** teaching strategies vary from one teacher to another means each teacher has his own method, for instance: the diversity of traditional and contemporary methods, in addition to the difference in curriculum regarding how to frame and organise cognitive activities and preparing lessons, these are the most prominent barriers that teachers can face among themselves.
- **Differences of carrier background:** Based on the teachers' previous experiences and skills in their professional path, the difference in their backgrounds can affect them through difficulty in discussion and a lack of understanding. In addition to the difference of settings, for instance, as reported by the participant (H): “their ways of thinking are not the same according to the difference in their environment.”

- **Diversity of interests and willingness:** In the context of teaching, enthusiasm varies from person to person, as the Italian proverb states: “A good teacher is like a candle—it consumes itself to light the way for others”. This quote is attributed to the group that sacrifices and knows the value of education well, and vice versa. According to the participants' answers, they argued that: “there are some teachers who are interested and passionate about collaborating with their colleagues, unlike others, who do not give any effort or value to this, which reduces the level of coordination among them”.

Question two: Are there any policies or initiatives from the administration to promote teacher collaboration?

Through this study, it was found that there is no support from the concerned parties that stimulates the collaboration process, except for discussions related to designing lessons and timetables. Most of the interviewees' answers affirmed that:” there are no initiatives that support the collaboration among teachers from the English department administration, except for meetings and councils that concern how to organise exams, but not related to lesson planning.”

In another statement, the teacher (E) mentioned that:” each specialisation has its own official who has periodic meetings with teachers by the administration, either by phone or by email.”

Question three: Does your current schedule allow sufficient time for collaboration with colleagues?

In this research, and due to the difference in timetables on the subject of collaboration, sometimes it can be said that it allows for some restrictions, such as the difference in academic semesters, which makes its practice difficult. The participants opinions are divided into two categories, some of them indicated that:” yes, my schedule allows me to collaborate and always there is time for collaboration” while the interviewee (I) identified that:” there is no opportunity

and enough time to collaborate due to the heavy workload and preoccupations outside of work, which makes collaboration almost impossible.”

Question four: Is there a need for an adequate physical space within the department dedicated to collaboration? If yes, what type of spaces would you suggest?

Physical spaces are one of the important factors that greatly influence the process of collaboration, the presence of specific spaces enhance and encourages teamwork and contributes to improve teaching methods, most teachers stated that the lack of physical spaces hinders communication among them, according to the participant (F) said that: “I highly welcome this idea, having a space would allow for unplanned and unformal collaboration.” according to their suggestions the interviewee (C) reported that:” I recommended assigning meeting rooms, laboratory, specific desks and offices in order to facilitate the process of discussion and understanding among them.”

Question five: Have you ever experienced a disagreement regarding teaching philosophies and instructional methods while working with colleagues?

At this point, it becomes clear that the differences of opinions or the multiplicity of teaching strategies are crucial in teaching philosophies, regarding teaching methodologies. A significant number of the responses provided by the interviewees emphasised one single factor, which is:

- **The variation of perspectives and backgrounds:** the diversity of opinions and backgrounds, especially among novice and experienced teachers, such as differences in contemporary teaching techniques compared to traditional ones.

The teacher (D) offered an opposing interpretation, explaining that:” Sometimes I face dissimilarities and diverging attitudes from my colleagues, but I never deemed it an obstacle to collaborating that we must overcome. On the contrary,

I believe that the university is the place where everybody has plainly to express ideas and display the philosophical doctrine they hold without any restriction.”

Question six: How does the feeling of trust among colleagues influence teacher collaboration?

Feeling confident is a key factor as it increases credibility, productivity, strengthens relationships among colleagues, and creates a sense of security when problems arise. Most of the answers were saying that everything is based on trust, the respondent (G) highlighted that: “the feeling of trust is essential and it can be a factor because trust is a communication of option, but it depends on the personality of the teacher.” Furthermore, the interviewee (D) added that:” feeling untrustworthy in every setting makes people act and not behave truly, and this is human nature in general. This may highly impact any collaboration initiative, especially in our department.”

Question seven: Would personality differences among teachers be considered a challenge to teacher collaboration? If yes, what types of differences could you describe?

The position of personal differences is a fundamental challenge to the challenges mentioned above, based on treatment and professional and human relationships.

Opinions vary depending on the situations the teacher (G) described: “sociability, some teachers prefer to work alone, scarcity of interaction, Lack of harmony among teachers, such as the idea of refusing to cooperate with others, different teaching methods, and diversity of knowledge and opinions. Gender differences: Male sensitivity towards women. psychological complexes, some of them reject the idea of to collaborate.” Moreover, the participant (C) noted: “Dogmatism means if I don’t discuss with you, I’m not going to teamwork.”

Question eight: Could you suggest any recommendations to promote and facilitate teacher collaboration within the department?

To be fully and powerfully engaged in shifting to the best, to have a great sense of communication, to sufficiently and attentively listen to others, and to accept others' character, ideas, and standpoints, these are the major things I embrace.

Organising workshops such as lesson design, promoting group activities, and mentoring for experienced teachers, with the aim of motivating and encouraging new teachers in their professional development.

Discussion

As mentioned earlier, the study aimed to measure the frequency of collaboration among EFL teachers in the Department of English at Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara, as well as to identify the challenges and barriers that may hinder effective collaboration. In addition, the research sought to shed light on the potential impact of Teacher Collaboration on teachers' professional performance, students' academic outcomes and the overall effectiveness of the university.

After analysing the results obtained from the two research tools, the questionnaire and the interview, the researchers obtained the final and convincing responses to the suggested research questions, mainly the first one: To what extent do teachers in the English Department at Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara engage in collaborative practices? The second: What are the main barriers that hinder collaboration among teachers in the English Department?

The results obtained from the questionnaire confirmed the first hypothesis, in which there is a limited extent of Teacher Collaboration in the department of English, the majority of teachers are likely to collaborate in informal and friendly ways in the absence of structured and

formal collaboration, which otherwise fosters professional development and, in turn, enhances learner outcomes. These findings align with those of Desta et al. (2023), who reported similarly limited collaboration among university teachers in the Amhara region of Ethiopia. In addition, the most commonly cited collaborative practices, according to the collected data, did not involve syllabus design, lesson planning or exams preparation which is far from the meaning of collaboration as defined by Johnstone and Tsai's (2018), teacher collaboration is “professional interaction with colleagues that focuses on refining and improving classroom instruction, curriculum, and supports for students” (P. 3). Besides, most of the teachers agreed that they don't collaborate with all their colleagues but typically with a few colleagues who were their former supervisors in the PhD or in some cases teachers of the same module, as is the case with translation and ESP teachers, who claimed that collaboration is among the 5 key roles of ESP teachers. Regarding co-teaching as a form of collaboration, none of the participants indicated that they had ever observed or participated in a colleague's lesson.

According to the results that emerged in the research, Teacher Collaboration is seen as having significant positive implications for both professional development and student learning. Many participants emphasised the value of shared insights and experiences gained through collaboration with colleagues. Although such collaborative experiences were relatively limited and noticed with few teachers, for instance, one teacher of “*Phonetics and Linguistics*” claimed that after the merger of the two modules, the participant who had previously taught only “*Linguistics*” benefited from the ideas and expertise of the “*Phonetics*” teacher. Although such cases demonstrating the advantages of collaboration were rare, all participants agreed on the significant benefits derived from such cooperative practices, according to Rosenholtz et al. (1958), ideas that are shaped through collaborative exchange of expertise, teaching materials and instructional methods that align pedagogical visions, appear to give rise to greater experimentation in classroom, greater teacher learning and certainly leads to a better problem

solving situations. This supports earlier research by Khasawneh et al. (2023). While much attention has been given to the benefits of teacher collaboration at the professional level of teachers, its positive impact on student outcomes and achievements should not be disregarded or neglected, although it may be difficult to measure it without an experiment, the majority of teachers emphasised and insisted on the importance of teacher collaboration on learners' outcomes and achievements. These findings align with those of Giles and Yazan (2023), who also highlighted the positive impact of teacher collaboration on student engagement and participation in the classroom through a collaborative process which included elements of collaborative planning, teaching, reflection, and assessment.

Moving to the second research question, which aimed to investigate the various barriers, obstacles and challenges that may hinder or undermine the collaborative practices among EFL teachers at the English Department. The interview served as a valuable tool for gathering in-depth insights and perspectives related to this aspect of the study.

The findings obtained from the interview confirmed the second hypothesis which was based on different studies (see Chapter Two), in which University EFL teachers' ability to collaborate is negatively influenced by several barriers, including: structural barriers, cultural barriers, and interpersonal barriers, with the emergence of additional hurdles which will be discussed in the subsequent points.

Time constraints: Among the research questions to answer, the most important challenges that prevent the process of collaboration among teachers. Through the questionnaire and interview tools, the current study found that the time constraint occupies the first place among the basic factors that hinder the communication process among teachers. Many colleagues have indicated that collaboration is among the effective and successful strategies and needs serious study, but its activation is difficult due to differences in work relationships and timetables, workload and

different work days. One of the teachers stated that: “there are those who work on Sundays and Mondays, in the same vein as the other who work on Wednesdays and Thursdays.” The difference is clear, so the opportunity for teamwork is very difficult. In addition, previous literature has mentioned that Teachers mostly have busy schedules filled with instructional duties, such as lesson preparation, grading and administrative responsibilities, leaving little room for collaborative activities (Lortie, 1975, p.179). In light of that, given the factors mentioned above, the possibility of meeting and discussing among teachers is negligible

Lack of administrative initiatives: The most interesting finding was the nonexistence of any administrative initiatives that support the idea of collaboration among teachers. It became clear from the statements of one of the participants: “The mood in the department does not motivate to collaborate”. In other words, there are only meetings and councils on how to organise exams, not within the framework of collaboration programs; there is no devoted time for collaboration. In a broader context, there is no actual training or specific lists for joint work. Administrative policies are an important and effective point in developing the collaboration strategy, and this is what the results of the current study confirmed. There is a very limited presence within the framework of administrative leadership, which indicates the absence of any activities and contributions that support the collaborative partnership. This result is consistent with what was reported by Cheng and Szeto (2016, as cited in Tosun & Bostanci, 2024) Enhancing leadership among teachers depends on the fundamental and effective importance of administrators in creating an educational framework that enhances all forms of cooperation processes, in addition to incorporating a culture of cooperation into educational policies and ensuring the support and encouragement of teachers who are given the opportunity for possible and fruitful leadership.

Personality differences: The principal insight revealed by the data was about personal differences within the framework of collaboration, which negatively affected the teaching process. As it is effective and fruitful, but the individual must confront some negative and

psychological obstacles that negatively impact the teaching process. Among the differences, one of the teachers stated: “Teacher collaboration is sometimes essential for professional development, but I usually prefer working alone to keep myself concentrated on what I do, far from others’ noisy data.” Here, desires vary according to the individual’s personality, as we find that there are some teachers who like to work individually, unlike the nature of the first category, which does not mind and desires to contribute actively and effectively in order to gain experience. Moreover, to the total rejection of discussion and collaboration means if I don’t discuss with you, I’m not going to team work due to the factor of trust. This results in a variety of teaching methods and approaches that affect the educational level and teamwork as a whole. These results of this study are consistent with those of other studies and suggest that. However, in the context of teacher collaboration, it requires mutual respect and trust, which can be hindered by personality differences or past conflicts among teachers (Little, 1990). Moreover, fear of revealing individuals’ weaknesses and mistakes leads to a feeling of vulnerability-based trust.

If teachers are to work collaboratively to clarify the essential learning for their courses and grade levels, write common assessments, and jointly analyse the results, they must overcome the fear that they may be exposed to their colleagues and principals as ineffective.

(DuFour et al., 2016, p.120)

Differences of carrier background: Another important finding was the nature of the teacher’s work environment, his experiences, knowledge, and even teaching methods. Many teachers mention that the element of cultural differences is due to different geographical dimensions. The culture of a person who grew up in the state of Mascara is completely different from the culture of another in the states of Oran and Tlemcen. In addition, their ways of thinking are not identical according to the diversity of their environments. Experience plays a fundamental and effective role also with regard to the time period in the professional path and teaching strategies

from the side of a novice and experienced teacher. At this point, the matter calls for discussion, respect, understanding and harmony among members in order to achieve creativity, which makes collaboration efforts faltering and ineffective.

The Influence of a Strong Ego: Alongside the intergenerational pedagogical conflict between novice and experienced teachers, the findings also highlighted a different form of tension or pedagogical conflict among teachers, this time stemming from a *strong ego* or, in other words, a *high level of self-esteem*. Some participants expressed hesitation to collaborate due to feelings of unequal treatment and a sense of diminished effectiveness in decision-making. As Schnathorst (2009) asserts, "Collaboration requires interactions between colleagues that are equally valued, as well as equal power in decision-making."

Novice Teachers Versus Experienced Teachers: The findings revealed the existence of an ongoing intergenerational pedagogical conflict between novice teachers and experienced teachers. This was particularly evident in the perspectives of novice teachers, who felt their voices remained unheard in the department and their pedagogical insights were not trustworthy. A participant claimed that they are subconsciously regarded as inferiors by experienced colleagues due to their former status as students. Few would contest the idea that novice teachers are in desperate need of the experience and knowledge of more experienced colleagues, as this helps them shorten their professional development process by avoiding repeated mistakes. It's like taking a shortcut. However, novice teachers also bring fresh perspectives, innovative ideas, and a greater familiarity with integrating ICTs into teaching, as highlighted by Celce-Murcia et al. (2014), "If you are an experienced teacher, you probably have different needs and interests than someone just starting out in the profession" (p. 631).

Lack of training: The standard preparation for a faculty career is taking undergraduate and graduate courses in your discipline and completing a research project on a topic someone else has defined. Once you join a faculty, your orientation may consist of nothing but the heading

of this section, and perhaps a half-day or a day on such things as health and retirement benefits and the importance of laboratory safety. The unstated assumption is that if you have a degree in a subject, you must know how to teach it at the college level.

For many university teachers, teaching is like being handed the keys to a car without being taught how to drive. Even experienced professors can wind up driving with their pedagogical parking brakes on. They steer forward clumsily, unaware that there's an easier way, and ignoring the smoke emerging from the tailpipe. In this context, Felder and Brent (2016) argue that teaching is a skill that must be developed and refined, just as any professional skill is. They also emphasise that university professors require specific training in pedagogy to enhance their teaching effectiveness; without training, even experienced teachers may struggle to design courses that meet the diverse needs of students, consequently impacting student success.

The Readiness and Willingness: Many teachers speak positively about collaboration in theory, yet in practice, they tend to favour working in isolation. During the interview, a considerable number of teachers stated that they prefer to be solely responsible for their modules and don't desire to have other teachers sharing the same modules with them, they implicitly and perhaps unconsciously, adopt the notion that they are not yet ready for collaborative work, even if they do not state this openly.

Limitations

The results of this study were subject to a set of limitations. For instance, some of the participants' answers to the questionnaire and interview may not be reliable and satisfactory, i.e., superficial answers of "yes" or "no" only, because they do not contain sufficient examples or precise explanations, which increases the possibility of ambiguity about the questions, in addition to their slowness in completing the online questionnaire. Another limitation is that

although the research tools are highly confidential and guarantee the preservation of participants' answers, there are some of them who relied entirely on written notes and their rejection of the idea of being audio recorded, which may affect the validity of data collection and interpretations and it is possible due to several factors such as: Lack of trust or maybe self-confidence. Moreover, this study faced another obstacle, which was the refusal and evasion of several teachers to take part in the interview process, which affects the credibility of the research findings and limits the sample size. The most important limitation lies in the fact that this study was subject to the difficulty of meeting teachers during the interviews due to time and their overloaded schedules, which limited the analysis process and the comprehensiveness of the results in general.

Recommendations

After identifying the most important obstacles that prevent the progress of the collaboration process among teachers in the previous headings, what is now required in this section is to prepare a set of recommendations for the purpose of strengthening the environment and collaborative efforts, adapting the teamwork strategy, and addressing the main shortcomings related to the subject of coordination.

- ***Overcoming time constraints:***

In order to improve the effectiveness and strategy of supporting coordination, the administration should take initiatives such as: organize schedules and divide hours from time to time within the framework of collaboration programs regarding the curriculum and lesson design in order to open the field of understanding and discussion between members and even exchange knowledge and experience in their teaching methods

- ***Addressing personality differences:***

Effective collaboration among colleagues requires resolving professional and personal differences resulting from a lack of comfort and trust in dealing with each other, which creates individual isolation. Therefore, it is also necessary to promote a culture of awareness and work to create a professional atmosphere characterised by dialogue and communication, regardless of their professional competencies and experience.

- ***Unifying Collaborative Efforts and Professional Harmony:***

Given the diversity of teaching philosophies and methods and the varying degrees of experience and knowledge among teachers, most educational institutions lack a mentoring policy among experienced and novice teachers. This is done to foster openness and promote a spirit of mutual respect, and enable them to understand the role of joint planning and work to unify viewpoints in an integrated manner.

- ***Adopting a Collaborative Program:***

Adopt or establish a structured collaboration program in which teachers regularly meet to share experiences, discuss student progress and achievements, and develop teaching strategies collaboratively. A program that establishes common shared goals and promotes a culture of continuous professional growth and collective responsibility for student outcomes. Caldwell and Spinks (1992) describe the worldwide move toward self-managing schools as a major trend in education. Currently, schools have significant authority in managing and overseeing their institutions in ways they believe will best contribute to their success.

- ***Working With Cells:***

Creating cells of teachers based on the subjects they are responsible for and the levels they are in charge of. These cells' objective is to meet regularly and agree on a unified syllabus to be delivered through the academic year, and unified lectures resulting in standardised exams that ensure consistent assessment of all students' learning outcomes.

- ***Provide An Ongoing Training for Working Teachers:***

For many university teachers, teaching is like being handed the keys to a car without being taught how to drive. Even experienced professors can wind up driving with their pedagogical parking brakes on. They steer forward clumsily, unaware that there's an easier way, and ignoring the smoke emerging from the tailpipe. In this context, Felder and Brent (2016) argue that teaching is a skill that must be developed and refined, just as any professional skill is. They also emphasise that university professors require specific training in pedagogy to enhance their teaching effectiveness; without training, even experienced teachers may struggle to design courses that meet the diverse needs of students, consequently impacting student success. Furthermore, Felder and Brent stress that institutions must invest in faculty development programs to ensure instructors are not only experts in their fields but also equipped to teach their subject matter effectively (Felder & Brent, 2016).

- ***Adopting “The Split-Course Model”:***

In many faculties, such as the Faculty of Science of Nature and Life at Mascara University, teaching is often divided into two main sessions: lectures and TPs (Tutorial Sessions or Practical Sessions). In this model, two teachers usually agree in advance on the program to be delivered through the semester or, in other cases, for the entire academic year. The content is presented in two sessions: the first one as lectures by a specific teacher most often a specialised professor, who introduces the key concepts of the lesson in a theoretical way with a large group of students in an amphitheatre then another session is led by another teacher with small groups of students in classrooms or laboratories to apply the knowledge taught in a very practical manner.

A very efficient strategy could be used in the department of English at the University of Mascara, mainly in Research Methodology modules, where most students face numerous

challenges while writing their graduation theses. The lessons can be approached using the split-course model, where one course, the Lecture session, is presented by a specific teacher to a large number of students in a theoretical way to introduce and explain the key points, while another teacher deals with the second session, the Tutorial Session to apply the knowledge taught in the lecture through activities, assignments or discussions in small groups to ensure deeper understanding and encourage participation. This teaching model can be applied with different modules, not specifically research methodology.

- ***Mandatory Teacher Collaboration:***

Through the interviews and questionnaires that were conducted, it became evident that the overwhelming majority of teachers are well aware of, and firmly convinced of, the benefits of working in teams. However, there appears to be a complete absence of any initiatives to engage in collaboration. Therefore, the researchers suggest that if collaboration were made compulsory by the Ministry of Higher Education, it might significantly facilitate and encourage its adoption among university teachers, just as it is already the case with the Ministry of Education and teachers at the primary, middle, and secondary schools.

Conclusion

To sum up, through analysing and interpreting the collected data of this study collected via the questionnaire and interview tools, this chapter demonstrated the great and effective importance of collaboration to English as a foreign language teachers and students. It also highlighted the most important obstacles and barriers that prevented the practice of teacher collaboration and which teachers faced, specifically the English Department at the University of Mascara. Moreover, this study presented a set of unique strategies and recommendations within the framework of strengthening cooperative partnerships, working to develop future prospects, and addressing all major shortcomings related to the field of coordination and

teamworking with regard to unifying cooperative efforts and adopting collaborative programs and joint planning.

GENERAL CONCLUSION

General Conclusion

To be a good teacher is a skill that is acquired through hard toil and personal endeavour. Most of all, it takes time to possess the skill that will differentiate an expert from a non-expert. Prior training is a must for any profession, let alone for teaching. We have highlighted the work of Felder and Brent (2016), which we think has hit the nail right on the head when saying teachers nowadays are hired and sent into their classrooms like they are given the keys to a car without ever having practised or being shown how to drive. Even experienced teachers can find themselves struggling, moving forward with difficulty, and unaware that there is a better way and a more efficient way to do things. This analogy reflects a key idea in this study that teaching is a skill that needs to be learnt, practised, shared, and improved over time. One of the most effective ways to do that is through collaboration with colleagues. Information and communication technologies, which have transformed our world into a global village, make it easy to collaborate with colleagues.

Teacher collaboration is an effective and successful strategy that aims to improve teachers' performance and skills and establish a high level of trust among them. In addition, it strengthens professional relationships and enhances opportunities for exchanging experiences and knowledge as a result of teamwork. Moreover, it provides a stimulating and appropriate environment that works to raise the level of teacher productivity. Collegial work serves to foster the development of the skills of creativity, discovery and critical thinking in teachers' psychology. For students, teacher collaboration appeared to be as beneficial as for teachers; it enhances students' outcomes and provides a supportive learning environment. The current study examined the extent of collaboration and contributed to exploring the most important barriers that prevent the collaboration process using English as a Foreign Language teachers in the

General Conclusion

English Department at the University of Mascara as a case study. The study focused on the following research questions:

1. To what extent do teachers in the English Department at Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara engage in collaborative practices?
2. What are the main barriers that hinder collaboration among teachers in the English Department?

The two research questions were guided by two different research tools: the questionnaire and the interview, which targeted EFL university teachers. The findings of the questionnaire uncover the reality of limited collaborative practices in all their forms among EFL university teachers in the Department of English at the University of Mascara, despite their full awareness of its importance on both levels, teachers' performance and students' achievements. This limited collaboration appeared as a result of several barriers and challenges. In addition, it highlights teachers' beliefs on the importance of teacher collaboration from various aspects and other beliefs related to their readiness and willingness for collaboration as well. A large number of teachers agreed on the importance of teacher collaboration at all levels and expressed that they are ready and willing to collaborate. However, their responses did not reflect the extent to which the collaboration is practised during their professional routine. The interview findings revealed several barriers and challenges that hinder teacher collaboration within the English Department, with the most significant being personality differences, lack of trust, insufficient administrative initiatives, time constraints, and a lack of effective training.

The selected research instruments were very helpful and effective in gathering reliable results despite the non-cooperation of some informants. The results obtained from this study confirmed both hypotheses, the first hypothesis, which suggested that EFL university teachers' collaborative practices within the department of English are rare and the second hypothesis,

General Conclusion

which suggested that this lack of collaborative practices among EFL university teachers appeared to be a result of different barriers categorised into three main categories: *structural* (such as time constraints and workload), *interpersonal* (such as personality differences and lack of trust) and *cultural* (such as differing pedagogical beliefs and resistance to change) hindrances based on several studies, Lortie (1975), Little (1990) and Schnathorst (2009). This study faced several limitations, the most important of which are teachers' superficial and unreliable answers, in addition to their delay in responding to the online questionnaire. This study also faced difficulty in scheduling interviews with participants due to their different schedules. In light of the results, the researchers proposed a set of recommendations and pedagogical suggestions that may enhance and promote effective teamwork and establish a supportive environment for collaboration.

The current study serves as the starting point for further research on teacher collaboration in higher education at Algerian universities. In this regard, the following topics could be proposed as potential areas for continuation: "Teacher Collaboration to Improve Students' Achievements", "Applying Teacher Collaboration in Thesis Supervision", and "Implementing the Collaborative Cycle model by Honigsfeld and Dove (2022) to Enhance Students' Writing." In addition, the researchers are advised to carry out experimental research on their investigations.

Finally, this study has presented that promoting teacher collaboration within Algerian EFL departments at Algerian universities holds great potential for enhancing both teacher performance and student outcomes. It is a concern that deserves urgent attention from educational stakeholders across the country.

References

References

Aliakbari, M., & Mansoori Nejad, A. (2013). On the effectiveness of team teaching in promoting learners' grammatical proficiency. *Canadian Journal of Education / Revue canadienne de l'éducation*, 36*(3), 5–22. <https://journals.sfu.ca/cje/index.php/cje-rce/article/view/1119/1593>

Almagro Esteban, A., & Vallejo Martos, M. C. (2002). A case study of collaboration among the ESP practitioner, the content teacher, and the students. *Revista Alicantina de Estudios Ingleses*, (15), 7–21. https://rua.ua.es/dspace/bitstream/10045/5250/1/RAEI_15_01.pdf

Ary, D., Jacobs, L. C., Sorensen, C. K., & Razavieh, A. (2010). *Introduction to research in education* (8th ed.). Wadsworth.

Bailey, K. D. (1994). *Methods of social research* (4th ed.). Free Press.

Ballantyne, K. G., Sanderman, A. R., & Levy, J. (2008). *Educating English language learners: Building teacher capacity* (Vol. 1). National Clearinghouse for English Language Acquisition. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED521360>

Benrabah, M. (2014). *Language conflict in Algeria: From colonialism to post-independence*. Multilingual Matters.

Caldwell, B. J., & Spinks, J. M. (1992). *Leading the self-managing school*. Routledge.

Celce-Murcia, M., Brinton, D. M., & Snow, M. A. (2014). *Teaching English as a second or foreign language* (4th ed.). National Geographic Learning / Cengage Learning.

Chapman, C., & Muijs, D. (2013). Does school-to-school collaboration promote school improvement? A study of the impact of school federations on student outcomes. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 24(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2013.840319>

Cochran-Smith, M. (1999). Learning to teach against the grain. *Harvard Educational Review*, 59(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.17763/haer.59.1.2031315x468w22u3>

Cochran-Smith, M., & Lytle, S. L. (1999). Relationships of knowledge and practice: Teacher learning in communities. *Review of Research in Education*, 24(1), 249–305. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0091732X024001249>

Cohen, D. K., & Hill, H. C. (1998). *Instructional policy and classroom performance: The mathematics reform in California* (CPRE Research Report Series RR-39). Consortium for Policy Research in Education. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED417942.pdf>

Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education* (8th ed.). Routledge.

References

- Cole, P. (2012). *Linking effective professional learning with effective teaching practice*. Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership (AITSL). <https://www.aitsl.edu.au/docs/default-source/default-document-library/professional-learning>
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Darling-Hammond, L., & Richardson, N. (2009). Teacher learning: What matters? *Educational Leadership*, 66(5), 46–53.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Wei, R. C., Andree, A., Richardson, N., & Orphanos, S. (2009). *Professional learning in the learning profession: A status report on teacher development in the United States and abroad*. National Staff Development Council. <https://learningforward.org/wp-content/uploads/2009/02/status-of-professional-learning-summary.pdf>
- Desta, S., Kassie, M., & Minten, B. (2023). *The status of teachers' collaboration in Ethiopian public universities found in the Amhara region*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366923943_The_status_of_teachers'_collaboration_in_Ethiopian_public_universities_found_in_the_Amhara_region
- Doppenberg, J. J., den Brok, P. J., & Bakx, A. W. E. A. (2012). Collaborative teacher learning in different primary school settings. *Teachers and Teaching*, 18(5), 547–566. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2012.709731>
- DuFour, R., DuFour, R., Eaker, R., & Many, T. (2016). *Learning by doing: A handbook for professional learning communities at work* (3rd ed.). Solution Tree Press.
- Felder, R. M., & Brent, R. (2016). *Teaching and learning STEM: A practical guide*. Jossey-Bass.
- Flinders, D. J. (1988). Teacher isolation and the new reform. *Journal of Curriculum and Supervision*, 4(1), 17–29. https://files.ascd.org/staticfiles/ascd/pdf/journals/jcs/jcs_1988fall_flinders.pdf
- Friend, M., & Bursuck, W. D. (2012). *Including students with special needs: A practical guide for classroom teachers* (6th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Fullan, M. (2000). The return of large-scale reform. *Journal of Educational Change*, 1(1), 5–28. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010068703786>
- Gherzouli, I. (2019). Educational reforms and language planning quandary in Algeria: An illustration with Arabization. *Sustainable Multilingualism*, (15), 27–45. <https://sciendo.com/pdf/10.2478/sm-2019-0012>

References

- Giles, A., & Yazan, B. (2023). The impact of teacher collaboration on ESL students' classroom participation: The case of Leo. *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research*, 11(2), 75–93. <https://doi.org/10.30466/ijltr.2023.121331>
- Goddard, Y. L., Goddard, R. D., & Tschannen-Moran, M. (2007). A theoretical and empirical investigation of teacher collaboration for school improvement and student achievement in public elementary schools. *Teachers College Record*, 109(4), 877–906. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146810710900401>
- Hochschild, J. L. (2009). Conducting intensive interviews and elite interviews. In M. Lamont & P. White (Eds.), *Workshop on interdisciplinary standards for systematic qualitative research* (pp. 124–127). National Science Foundation. https://www.academia.edu/107112665/Conducting_Intensive_Interviews_and_Elite_Interviews
- Honigsfeld, A., & Dove, M. G. (2010). *Collaboration and co-teaching: Strategies for English learners*. SAGE Publications.
- Johnston, W., & Tsai, T. (2018). *The prevalence of collaboration among American teachers: National findings from the American Teacher Panel* (RR-2217-RC). RAND Corporation. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RR2217.html
- Kennedy, M. M. (2016). How does professional development improve teaching? *Review of Educational Research*, 86(4), 945–980. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654315626800>
- Khasawneh, Y. J. A., Alsarayreh, R., Al Ajlouni, A. A., Eyadat, H. M., Ayasrah, M. N., & Khasawneh, M. A. S. (2023). An examination of teacher collaboration in professional learning communities and collaborative teaching practices. *Journal of Education and e-Learning Research*, 10*(3), 446–452. <https://doi.org/10.20448/jeelr.v10i3.4841>
- Kiel, E. (2020). Teacher collaboration as a core objective of school development: A study of patterns in perceptions of collaboration and its perceived benefits. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 35(3), 547–567. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2020.1747501>
- Killion, J. (2012). *Meet the promise of content standards: Tapping technology to enhance professional learning*. Learning Forward. <https://learningforward.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/tapping-technology-to-enhance-professional-learning.pdf>
- Kohm, B., & Nance, B. (2009). Creating collaborative cultures. *Educational Leadership*, 66(5), 67–72.
- Kolleck, N. (2019). Motivational aspects of teacher collaboration. *Frontiers in Education*, 4, Article 122. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2019.00122>

References

- Kumar, R. (2011). *Research methodology: A step-by-step guide for beginners* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Lassonde, C. A., & Israel, S. E. (2009). *Teacher collaboration for professional learning: Facilitating study, research, and inquiry communities*. Jossey-Bass.
- Little, J. W. (1990). The persistence of privacy: Autonomy and initiative in teachers' professional relations. *Teachers College Record*, 91(4), 509–536.
- Liu, L. (2008). Co-teaching between native and non-native English teachers: An exploration of co-teaching models and strategies in the Chinese primary school context. *Reflections on English Language Teaching*, 7(2), 103–118. <https://www.nus.edu.sg/celec/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/103-118liu.pdf>
- Lortie, D. C. (1975). *Schoolteacher: A sociological study*. University of Chicago Press.
- Louis, K. S., Marks, H. M., & Kruse, S. D. (1996). Teachers' professional community in restructuring schools. *American Educational Research Journal*, 33(4), 757–798. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312033004757>
- Lowe, N. K. (2019). What is a pilot study? *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 48(2), 117–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2019.01.005>
- Lyle, S. (2009). Teacher research as professional development. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 90(8), 584–592. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003172170909000808>
- McKinsey & Company. (2007). *How the world's best-performing school systems come out on top*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/education/our-insights/how-the-worlds-best-performing-school-systems-come-out-on-top>
- Montgomery, M. S., & Akerson, A. (2019). Facilitating collaboration through a co-teaching field experience. *Networks: An Online Journal for Teacher Research*, 21(1), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.4148/2470-6353.1284>
- Rosenholtz, S. J., Bassler, O., & Hoover-Dempsey, K. (1985). Organizational conditions of teacher learning. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 2(2), 91–104. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0742-051X\(86\)90008-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0742-051X(86)90008-9)
- Sai, X., & Siraj, S. (2015). Professional learning community in education: Literature review. *The Online Journal of Quality in Higher Education*, 2(2), 65–78. <https://www.tojqih.net/journals/tojqih/articles/v02i02/v02i02-07.pdf>

References

- Saleem, A., Kausar, H., & Deeba, F. (2021). Social constructivism: A new paradigm in teaching and learning environment. *Perennial Journal of History*, 2(2), 403–421. <https://doi.org/10.52700/pjh.v2i2.86>
- Sánchez-Cardona, I., Sanchez-Lugo, J., & Velez, J. (2012). Exploring the potential of communities of practice for learning and collaboration in a higher education context. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 1820–1825. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.05.385>
- Schleifer, D., Rinehart, C., & Yanisch, T. (2017). *Teacher collaboration in perspective: A guide to research*. Public Agenda; Spencer Foundation. <https://publicagenda.org/resource/teacher-collaboration-in-perspective/>
- Schmoker, M. J. (1999). *Results: The key to continuous school improvement* (2nd ed.). Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Schnathorst, J. S. (2009). *Teacher collaboration: Why isn't it working?* [Master's thesis, University of Northern Iowa]. UNI ScholarWorks. <https://scholarworks.uni.edu/grp/1476>
- Shakenova, L. (2017). The theoretical framework of teacher collaboration. *Khazar Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 20(2), 34–48. <https://jhss-khazar.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/2.Lyaila.20.02.2017.2.pdf>
- Smith, R. (2020). *Mentoring teachers to research their classrooms: A practical handbook*. British Council.
- Stehr-Green, P. A., Stehr-Green, J. K., & Nelson, A. (2003). Developing a questionnaire. In P. D. M. MacDonald (Ed.), *FOCUS on Field Epidemiology* (Vol. 2, Issue 2). North Carolina Center for Public Health Preparedness, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. <http://www.sph.unc.edu/nccphp/focus/>
- Tosun, A., & Bozkurt Bostancı, A. (2024). The role of administrative support in the relationship between teachers' perceptions of organizational support and teacher leadership levels. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.202428306>
- Vangrieken, K., Dochy, F., Raes, E., & Kyndt, E. (2015). Teacher collaboration: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/275723807>
- Ventura, S., & Ventura, M. (2022). *Achievement teams: How a better approach to PLCs can improve student outcomes and teacher efficacy*. ASCD.
- Yin, R. K. (1994). *Case study research: Design and methods* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications.

Appendices

Appendix A

Questionnaire

Dear teachers,

You are kindly invited to participate in this questionnaire, which serves as a data-gathering tool. It aims to collect information needed for our research entitled: "University Teachers' Attitudes Towards Teacher Collaboration." We would be pleased if you could help us obtain the appropriate answers to our suggested questions.

This questionnaire will take less than 20 minutes of your time, and your answers will be kept strictly confidential. The provided information will be used solely for academic purposes.

Your contribution is highly appreciated and valuable for our research. Thank you.

Section One: Teachers' profile and personal information

Gender: Male Female

Years of experience: less than 5 years from 5 to 10 years more than 10 years

Specialities in charge of:

Modules in charge of:

Levels in charge of:

Section Two: Teachers' Collaboration Frequency

	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
I collaborate with my colleagues from the same department.					
I work with my colleagues from the same speciality.					
I work with my colleagues from the same levels.					
I work with my colleagues teaching the same modules.					
I work only with one or two of my colleagues.					
I engage with my colleagues in lesson planning.					
I discuss teaching methods and strategies with my colleagues.					
I participate in peer observation or co teaching sessions.					

I discuss my learners' achievements with my colleagues					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Section Three: Teacher Collaboration Barriers and Challenges

- What are the main obstacles to teacher collaboration?

- Time constraints
- Lack of administrative support.
- Different teaching philosophy and strategies.
- Limited physical spaces for collaboration. (e.g., staff room, cafeteria)
- Lack of trust.
- Personality differences.
- other obstacles are not mentioned above (please specify):

.....
.....
.....

(You can select more than one option)

Section Four: Teachers' Beliefs and Teacher Collaboration Benefits

1- Do you believe that Teacher Collaboration is essential for professional development and improves teaching qualities?

Yes No

2- Do you believe that Teacher Collaboration enhances students' outcomes?

Yes No

3- Do you believe that Teacher Collaboration is crucial for school (university) development and effectiveness?

Yes No

4- Do you believe that Teacher Collaboration fosters positive and supportive work environment?

Yes No

5- If given the opportunity and the right conditions, would you like to collaborate more with your colleagues?

Yes

No

Appendix B

Interview

Good morning, sir/madam,

You are kindly invited to respond to a set of questions and share your valuable insights regarding your experiences and perspectives on Teacher Collaboration in the Department of English at the University of Mascara.

Section One: Teachers' Background and Experiences with Teacher Collaboration

1. How long have you been teaching English at the University?
2. Have you participated in any form of collaboration? if yes, what are the teaching activities have you participated in as part of a team?
3. Do you feel comfortable working in teams? Why or why not?

Section Two: Teacher Collaboration Importance

4. Do you believe that Teacher collaboration is important for your professional development? how?
5. In your opinion, can teacher collaboration play an important role in enhancing student outcomes and promoting their achievements? If yes, how?

Section Three: Teacher Collaboration Barriers.

6. Do you believe that teacher collaboration in the department can be hindered by certain barriers or obstacles? If yes, could you describe some of these challenges?
7. Are there any policies or initiatives from the administration to promote Teacher Collaboration?
8. Does your current schedule allow sufficient time for collaboration with colleagues?
9. In your opinion, is there a need for an adequate physical space within the department dedicated to collaboration? If yes, what type of spaces would you suggest?
10. Have you ever experienced a disagreement regarding teaching philosophies and instructional methods while working with colleagues?

11. How does the feeling of trust among colleagues influence Teacher Collaboration?
12. Would personality differences among teachers be considered a challenge to Teacher Collaboration? If yes, what types of differences could you describe?
13. Are there any additional barriers to teacher collaboration we haven't discussed and you want to add

الملخص

لا شك في أن مهنة التعليم تُعد ممارسة مرهقة تتطلب الوقت والجهد والصبر. ويُفترض أن يُنظر إلى وجود زميل أو فريق عمل يشارك الأعباء ويوفر الدعم كمكسب ثمين، لا عبئًا كما يعتقد بعض الأساتذة. تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى استكشاف مدى التعاون بين الأساتذة في قسم اللغة الإنجليزية بجامعة معسكر، كما تسعى إلى تحديد العوامل التي قد تُثبط أو تُعيق أساتذة اللغة الإنجليزية كلغة أجنبية في القسم من ممارسة التعاون، والذي يُعد متغيرًا مهمًا في تحسين أداء الأساتذة، وتعزيز بيئة تعليمية قوية، وتحقيق نتائج أفضل لدى الطلبة.

ولمعالجة هذه الإشكالية، اعتمد الباحثون منهجًا ذو طابعين كمي و كفي لجمع بيانات موثوقة وموضوعية، وذلك باستخدام أداتين بحثيتين: الاستبيان والمقابلة، مع عينة مكونة من 60 أستاذًا لتعليم اللغة الإنجليزية كلغة أجنبية في قسم اللغة الإنجليزية بجامعة معسكر.

وقد كشفت النتائج عن وجود تعاون محدود بين الأساتذة، ويُعزى ذلك إلى مجموعة من العوائق الهيكلية، والشخصية، والثقافية. وبذلك تكون الدراسة قد حققت هدفها. وبناءً على هذه النتائج، تقترح الدراسة عدة توصيات عملية موجهة للأساتذة وصانعي السياسات على حد سواء لتعزيز ثقافة التعاون بين الأساتذة في القسم، وتجاوز العقبات المحددة، إلى جانب مقترحات تربوية تهدف إلى ترسيخ مبدأ التعاون على مستوى قسم اللغة الإنجليزية.

Résumé

Il est indéniable que l'enseignement est une pratique exigeante, nécessitant temps, effort et patience. Avoir un collègue ou une équipe pour partager la charge de travail et offrir un soutien mutuel devrait être perçu comme un atout précieux, et non comme un fardeau, contrairement à ce que certains enseignants peuvent penser. Cette étude explore la fréquence de la collaboration entre les enseignants du département d'anglais de l'université de Mascara. Elle vise également à identifier les facteurs susceptibles de freiner cette collaboration chez les enseignants d'anglais langue étrangère (ALE), bien que celle-ci soit reconnue comme un levier essentiel pour améliorer les pratiques pédagogiques, renforcer le climat éducatif et favoriser la réussite des apprenants. Pour répondre à cette problématique, les chercheurs ont adopté une approche méthodologique mixte, combinant des méthodes quantitatives et qualitatives, à travers deux outils principaux : un questionnaire et un entretien, administrés à un échantillon de 60 enseignants d'ALE du département. Les résultats révèlent une collaboration limitée entre les enseignants, attribuable à des obstacles structurels, interpersonnels et culturels. Ainsi, cette étude atteint pleinement son objectif. En réponse à ces conclusions, des recommandations concrètes sont proposées à l'intention des enseignants et des responsables pédagogiques. Celles-ci visent à encourager la collaboration et à surmonter les obstacles identifiés, ainsi qu'à mettre en œuvre des propositions pédagogiques spécifiques pour renforcer la collaboration au sein du département d'anglais.